

**STUDIES ON ASSOCIATIVE GROWTH OF
Lactobacillus acidophilus AND *Lactobacillus casei* TO
DEVELOP YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT**

Thesis

SUBMITTED TO THE

**G.B. Pant University of Agriculture &
Technology**

PANTNAGAR-263 145, (U.P.) INDIA

By

Manoj Kumar

**IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE DEGREE OF**

Master of Science

(FOOD TECHNOLOGY)

SEPTEMBER, 1996

Dr. Y.K. Jha
Assoc. Professor

Department of Food Science & Tech.
College of Agriculture
G.B. Pant Univ. of Agric. & Tech.
Pantnagar-263 145, U.S. Nagar, UP

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "**STUDIES ON ASSOCIATIVE GROWTH OF *Lactobacillus acidophilus* AND *Lactobacillus casei* TO DEVELOP YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT**", submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of **Master of Science** with major in **Food Technology** of the College of Post Graduate Studies, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, is a record of bona fide research carried out by Mr. **Manoj Kumar**, Id.No. **17855**, under my supervision, and no part of the thesis has been submitted for any other degree or diploma.

The assistance and help received during the course of investigation and sources of literature have been duly acknowledged.

(Y.K. JHA)
Chairman
Advisory Committee

CERTIFICATE

We, the undersigned, Members of the Advisory Committee of **MR. Manoj Kumar, Id.No. 17855**, a candidate for the degree of **Master of Science** with major in **Food Technology** agree that the thesis entitled "**STUDIES ON ASSOCIATIVE GROWTH OF *Lactobacillus acidophilus* AND *Lactobacillus casei* TO DEVELOP YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT**" may be submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree.

(Y.K. Jha)
Chairman

(Nirankar Nath)
Member

(Gurmukh Singh)
Member

(D.C. Thapliyal)
Member

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Appreciation is expressed to the many persons, who contributed generously of their time and efforts towards this investigation, special gratitude to **Dr. B.K. Mital** (Professor, Department of Food Science and Technology) and **Dr. Y.K. Jha** (Associate Professor, Department of Food Science and Technology and Chairman of advisory committee). The work owes its inception to Dr. B.K. Mital and its final form to Dr. Y.K. Jha. Though I feel that worldly thanks can hardly express my gratitude, yet I wish to place on record my deep sense of regard for them.

I wish to thank the members of the advisory committee for their support extended during the entire course of this investigation.

Dr. Narankar Nath, Professor and Head, Deptt. of Food Science and Technology,

Dr. D.C. Thapaliyal, Associate Professor, Deptt. of Epidemiology & Public Health, College of Veterinary Sciences,

Dr. Gurumukh Singh, Associate Professor, Deptt. of Food Science and Technology.

Thanks are due to Dean, College of P.G.S.; Dean, College of Agriculture; Assistant Director, Livestock Research Centre of the University for providing the necessary facilities for the research work.

I express my heartfelt gratitude to Dr. G.C. Gupta, Dr. P.K. Gupta, College of Veterinary Science for their advice and suggestions, that greatly improved the final product.

Finally, but most important, I wish to extend appreciation to my family members for their patience and encouragement. My parents have been supportive on a daily basis for which I am grateful. To them, I dedicate my thesis.

(Manoj Kumar)
Author

Pantnagar
September, 96

ABSTRACT

The present investigation was undertaken to develop a yoghurt-like product using *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei* as starter cultures in place of the conventional yoghurt organisms *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus*. Different strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* were evaluated for their growth characteristics, acid production, bile tolerance, cholesterol uptake, survival at different pH levels and antagonistic activity against selected pathogenic bacteria.

Among the strains tested, *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS were found to be superior acid producers individually as well as in combination. Optimization studies revealed that the most suitable conditions for manufacture of yoghurt-like product were cow milk containing 2 per cent fat, supplementation with 5 per cent sugar and 5 per cent skim milk powder, inoculation with a mixed starter culture of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS at 3 per cent (1:1), and incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 hours.

The selected *L. casei* strains exhibited tolerance to bile salts and demonstrated cholesterol uptake ability. *L. acidophilus*-I showed inhibitory activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi*, whereas *L. casei*-RTS did not exhibit antagonistic activity against the pathogens tested.

Growth studies indicated rapid increases in viable count, titratable acidity, lactose utilization, soluble nitrogen and acetaldehyde production during incubation. The yoghurt-like product prepared using the selected strains was comparable to regular yoghurt with respect to composition, colour, flavour and taste. During storage at $5\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, the product remained acceptable for up to six days and exhibited progressive increases in titratable acidity, soluble nitrogen, sugar utilization and acetaldehyde content.

The study demonstrated that a satisfactory yoghurt-like product possessing desirable sensory quality and potential probiotic attributes can be successfully prepared using a mixed culture of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-I and *Lactobacillus casei*-RTS.

Keywords: *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, yoghurt-like product, probiotic cultures, antagonistic activity, cholesterol uptake, sensory evaluation.

Table of Content

1. INTRODUCTION.....	8
2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	11
2.1 Characteristics	11
2.2 Growth requirements	13
2.3 Acidophilus based products.....	15
3. MATERIALS AND METHODS	25
3.1 Milk	25
3.2 Cultures.....	25
3.3 Media	25
3.4 Litmus milk.....	25
3.5 Chemicals	25
3.6 Analytical determinations.....	26
3.7 Characterization of strains	29
3.8 Product preparation.....	33
3.9 Product evaluation	34
3.10 Statistical analysis.....	34
4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	35
4.1 Effect of type of milk on per cent titratable acidity.....	35
4.2 Effect of fat levels on acid production.....	39
4.3 Effect of sugar on acid production.....	41
4.4 Effect of inoculum rate on acid production.....	42
4.5 Effect of incubation temperature on acid production	44
4.6 Effect of total solids on acid production.....	46
4.7 Effect of different pH and bile salt concentrations on the growth of <i>L. casei</i> strains during 16 hrs incubation at 37°C.....	47
4.8 Cholesterol uptake	52
4.9 Antagonistic activity.....	53
4.10 Studies on growth characteristics of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I and <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination in standardized cow milk.....	56
4.11 Storage Studies	62
4. SUMMARY	68
5. LITERATURE CITED	70
VITA.....	80
Special appreciation.....	80

List of Tables

Table 4.1: Effect of different strains of <i>L. acidophilus</i> and <i>L. casei</i> on titratable acidity and pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	35
Table 4.2: Effect of different strains of <i>L. acidophilus</i> and <i>L. casei</i> in combinations on titratable acidity and pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	36
Table 4.3: Effect of fat levels on titratable acidity of cow milk using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	39
Table 4.4: Effect of sugar levels on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	41
Table 4.5: Effect of inoculum rate of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination on titratable acidity of cow skim milk during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	43
Table 4.6: Effect of incubation temperature on titratable acidity, produced by <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination in cow skim milk.....	44
Table 4.7: Effect of skim milk powder addition on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	46
Table 4.8: Survivability of <i>L. casei</i> -RTS in lactic broth at different pH during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	48
Table 4.9: Survivability of <i>L. casei</i> -300 in lactic broth at different pH during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	48
Table 4.10: Survivability of <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and <i>L. casei</i> -300 in lactic broth containing 0.3 % sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	50
Table 4.11: Growth inhibition of <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and <i>L. casei</i> -300 in presence of sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	51
Table 4.12: Uptake of cholesterol by different <i>L. casei</i> strains	52
Table 4.13: Inhibitory zones for different pathogenic bacteria, developed by milk culture filtrate obtained from <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I	55
Table 4.14: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	56
Table 4.15: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of <i>L. casei</i> -RTS at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$...	57
Table 4.16: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I and <i>L. casei</i> -RTS in combination at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	59
Table 4.17: Proximate Composition of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product.....	62
Table 4.18: Acceptability Scores of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	64
Table 4.19: Biochemical changes in yoghurt and yoghurt like product during storage at $5\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	65

List of Figures

Figure 4.1: Effect of different strains of <i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> and <i>Lactobacillus casei</i> on titratable acidity of cow and buffalo skim milk during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	37
Figure 4.2: Effect of different strains of <i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> and <i>Lactobacillus casei</i> on pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	37
Figure 4.3: Effect of different fat levels on titratable acidity of cow milk, using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	40
Figure 4.4: Effect of sugar levels on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	42
Figure 4.5: Effect of inoculum rate of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination on titratable acidity of cow skim milk during 16 h incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	43
Figure 4.6: Effect of incubation temperature on titratable acidity, produced by <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination in cow skim milk	45
Figure 4.7: Effect of total solid content on titratable acidity of cow skim milk, using <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	47
Figure 4.8: Effect of <i>L. casei</i> strains on optical density of lactic broth at different pH during incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	49
Figure 4.9: Effect of <i>L. casei</i> strains on optical density of lactic broth containing 0.3 per cent sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	50
Figure 4.10: Inhibitory zones developed by milk culture filtrate of (A) <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I and (B) <i>L. casei</i> -RTS against pathogenic bacteria	54
Figure 4.11: Inhibitory zones developed by milk culture filtrate of (A) <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I and (B) <i>L. casei</i> -RTS against <i>Salmonella typhi</i>	54
Figure 4.13: The changes in population of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	60
Figure 4.14: Titratable acidity developed by <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	60
Figure 4.15: Per cent lactose utilization by <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	61
Figure 4.16: Effect of <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination on per cent soluble nitrogen during 16 hrs of incubation at $42\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	61
Figure 4.17: Acetaldehyde produced by <i>L. acidophilus</i> -I, <i>L. casei</i> -RTS and their combination during 16 hrs of incubation at $42\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	62
Figure 4.18: Changes in Sensory Characteristics of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	64
Figure 4.19: Changes in Titratable Acidity and Soluble Nitrogen of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	66
Figure 4.20: Changes in Sugar Utilization and Acetaldehyde content of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$	66

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the turn of the century, efforts are being made all over the world to unveil the therapeutic and nutritional potentials of different lactic acid bacteria, as they have tremendous public health significance. Many research reports have confirmed the concept that effects of toxic substances produced by harmful bacteria affecting man's health could be combated by lactic acid bacteria particularly *Lactobacilli*. Therefore, the presence of *Lactobacilli* in the intestinal tract has been claimed to contribute to the well being of men.

It has been observed that *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*, the essential fermenting organism in yoghurt manufacture is unable to proliferate or even survive for a longer period in human intestinal tract because of low surface tension and lack of nutrients. Therefore, efforts are made to find a *Lactobacillus* which could successfully survive in gastrointestinal tract and proliferate. Subsequent researches have shown that *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* are not only capable of colonizing the intestinal tract but also exert antagonistic action against food-borne and intestinal pathogens and stabilize normal intestinal flora. In addition, these organisms have been shown to possess anticarcinogenic and hypocholesterolemic properties.

Acceptable yoghurt like products can be manufactured by using *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei* strains. The problems encountered in the manufacture of such type of products using these organisms are (i) slow rate of acid production (ii) susceptibility of the organisms to high acidity, and (iii) lack of acceptable flavour and texture. Hence, such products lack wide acceptability and their consumption often linked to therapeutic properties rather than to organoleptic appeal. Since the characteristics of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* are not well defined. Therefore, many times strains have been used which do not have desired beneficial properties. This has led to many conflicting reports about the usefulness of these organisms as dietary adjuncts. Therefore, it is desirable that available *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* strains are characterized and the most appropriate combinations used in the manufacture of products. Consequently, the present investigation was under taken to select the strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* to manufacture yoghurt like product. The specific objectives were to -

1. Select strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* to manufacture yoghurt like product.

2. Determine the effect of fat, sugar, total solids, inoculum rate and incubation temperature in milk on growth of selected strains and their combination in cow milk.
3. Study their pH and bile tolerance, cholesterol uptake and antagonistic behaviour against common food-borne and intestinal pathogens.
4. Prepare a yoghurt like product, using the selected strains and evaluate its acceptability against regular yoghurt.
5. Compare the sensory and biochemical characteristics of prepared product with regular yoghurt during storage at $5\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The virtues of fermented milk foods were known to man even during the ancient days of civilization. In earlier days, these milk foods were produced by natural fermentations with the main objective of preserving milk. Latter the nutritive and therapeutic characteristics of fermented milk foods were actively studied, yet the basis of enhancing longevity and treatment of serious body ailments has not been clearly understood (Deeth and Tamime, 1981). Researches conducted during last decade have greatly enhanced our understanding about the health promoting properties of these products. It is now well recognized that consumption of fermented milks is helpful in maintaining good health, restoring body vigour and in combating intestinal and other disease disorders (Gilliland, 1979; Sandine, 1979). Among fermented milks, the therapeutic value of acidophilus milk products has focussed greater attention of investigators because of their wide ranging effects (Speck, 1980; Nashisi, 1986; Gilliland, 1989). The possible benefits which occur on consumption of acidophilus milk products include stabilization of intestinal microflora, control of intestinal and other infections, control of serum cholesterol, prevention of colon cancer and enhanced nutrient availability.

Although acidophilus milk products have attracted the attention as a health food in many countries for more than half a century, a product using *L. acidophilus* and/or *L. casei* as the fermenting organism(s) having wide consumer appeal has yet to be developed. However, the research conducted in the recent past have greatly enhanced our understanding about the criteria for selecting *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* strains possessing beneficial properties and their usage in manufacturing of products. These aspects are briefly reviewed here.

2.1 Characteristics

2.1.1 Genus *Lactobacillus*

Lactobacilli are Gram-positive rods, typically non-motile, non sporulating and non-acid fast. They are aerobic and facultatively anaerobic, catalase negative and grow best at pH 6.0. The carbohydrates and polyalcohols are changed by homofermentation to lactic acid or by heterofermentation to lactic acid, acetic acid, alcohols and carbon dioxide. Surface growth is enhanced on enriched media and under anaerobic conditions with added CO₂ (5-10 %). Orala-Jensen (1919) designated the homofermentative rod-shaped lactic acid bacteria with optimum

temperatures around 40°C, as *Thermobacterium*, whereas those with optimum temperatures near 30°C were streptobacterium. The heterofermentative rods were designated as *Betabacterium*. *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, and *Lactobacillus helveticus* are typical homofermentative *Lactobacilli* of interest to the dairy microbiologist. Briggs (1954) reported the presence of *Lactobacilli* in feeds, silage, manure, milk and its products, grain and meat products, water, sewage, beer, wine, fruits and fruit juices, pickled vegetables; also parasitic in the mouth, intestinal tract and vagina of many homothermic animals including man. The G + C content of the DNA ranges from 34.7±1.4 to 53.4±0.5 moles % (buoyant density).

2.1.1.1 *Lactobacillus casei*

Description based on the observations of Orla-Jensen (1919), Dorothy and Wheater (1855) *Lactobacillus casei* is a gram-positive, non-motile, asporogenous, rod-shaped organism generally less than 1.5 µm wide, forms short chains of cells in milk and longer chains in broth cultures.

This organism is microaerophilic and has an optimum growth temperature of 30°C with a range of 10°C to 40°C. A few strains may survive 63°C for 30 minutes but none survive 60°C for 90 minutes. Penicillin in concentrations of 0.3 to 0.6 units per milliliter or streptomycin in concentrations of 5 µg per milliliter inhibits this organism, but various strains will grow in the presence of 5.5 per cent salt. *Lactobacillus casei* grows well in milk and produces up to 1.5 per cent acid in it, and upon prolonged incubation of milk, especially in the presence of calcium carbonate, an increase in soluble nitrogen may be observed.

Cell-free extracts of *Lactobacillus casei* contain proteolytic enzymes active on casein, gelatin, DL-leucylglycylglycine, glycyl-L-leucine, and DL-alanyl-glycine, but not on D-leucyl-L-tyrosine. This species apparently possesses proteinase, aminopolypeptidase, and dipeptidase, but not carboxypolypeptidase (Gonshery and Hansen, 1951).

Three subspecies were recognized by Rogosa et al. (1953), *L. casei* subsp. *casei*, *L. casei* subsp. *alactosus*, and *L. casei* subsp. *rhamnosus*. These subspecies show highly unusual characteristics. At least 90 % of the strains of these three subspecies grow at the expense of and ferment pyruvate; all other *Lactobacilli* are negative. *L. casei* subsp. *alactosus* does not ferment lactose.

Abo-Elnaga and Kandler (1965) described four strains of *L. casei* subsp. *rhamnosus* fermenting arabinose. This result is highly unusual.

Lactobacillus casei is isolated from milk, dairy products and dairy environments, sour dough, cowdung, silage, human mouth, human intestinal contents, stools and the human vagina. This species has never been isolated from oral or intestinal samplings from the rat, hamster, mouse or rabbit.

2.1.1.2 *Lactobacillus acidophilus*

Curran et al. (1993); Titteslar et al. (1947); Rogosa et al. (1953) and Hansen et al. (1970) described *Lactobacillus acidophilus* as Gram-positive rod, with rounded ends, generally 0.6-0.9 x 1.5-1.6 μm in size, occurring singly, in pairs or short chains, nonmotile, non-flagellated, nonsporulating and catalase negative. It does not contain cytochromes and therefore, is benzidine negative, with respect to oxygen requirement, *L. acidophilus* is microaerophilic and surface growth on solid media is generally enhanced by anaerobiosis or reduced oxygen pressure and 5-10 % CO_2 .

The energy yielding metabolism in *L. acidophilus* is fermentative. Orla-Jensen (1919) designated this organism as homofermentative as glucose is almost quantitatively converted to racemic mixture of lactic acid. However, there are conflicting reports about the proportion of L(+) and L(-) isomers of lactic acid produced. Among the two (L+) isomer has been reported to be predominant (Benner, 1975; Wiesner et al. 1975). However, Johnson et al. (1980) found that majority of the *L. acidophilus* strains produce nearly equal amounts of the two isomers or a slight excess of the D(-). Orla-Jensen (1943) grouped this organism in the subgenus *thermobacterium* as it did not grow at 15°C. However, profuse growth of this organism occurs at 35-40°C.

2.2 Growth requirements

2.2.1 Carbohydrates

Variety of carbohydrates such as glucose, galactose, fructose and disaccharides-lactose, sucrose, maltose is fermented and is utilized as the source of energy by *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei*. These sugars occur in commonly consumed foods.

Since lactose, also known as milk sugar, virtually present in milk, is fermented by lactic acid bacteria provides the basis for large segment of dairy industry in most of the countries. The principal product of its fermentation, lactic acid contributes to the flavour, texture and keeping quality of the final product. Hydrolysis of lactose yields glucose and galactose. Since *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus* are homofermentative, they metabolize glucose through Embden Meyerhof Parnas pathway and form lactic acid as virtually the sole end product. Galactose is metabolized by *Lactobacilli* via Leloir pathway (Eskin et al., 1971; Gottsahalk, 1986).

Hansen and Lessel (1971) found that maltose and sucrose were usually utilized by some strains of *L. casei*, however, fermentation may be slow. Srinivas et al. (1890) found the order of utilization of sugars by *L. acidophilus* which was glucose \geq fructose > sucrose > lactose.

2.2.2 Minerals

The requirements of magnesium and manganese for the growth of *Lactobacilli* have been documented by many researchers (Orla-Jensen, 1943; Rogosa et al., 1953; DeMan et al., 1960).

Wooley (1941) reported that manganese stimulated the growth of *L. acidophilus*. Sabine and Vaselekos (1867) found that *L. acidophilus* required both magnesium and manganese for its growth. Grebus et al. (1867) observed that in addition to magnesium, manganese and iron also promoted the growth of *L. acidophilus*.

2.2.3 Amino acids and Vitamins

The *Lactobacilli* have limited synthetic capabilities thus these organisms need exogenous supply of amino acids and vitamins for their growth. The glutamic acid, arginine, phenylalanine, histidine, leucine, proline, tryptophan and valine were essential for the growth of *L. acidophilus* (Guirard, 1974; Ledesma et al., 1977) and cysteine accelerated its growth (Marshall et al., 1982).

Among the vitamins, pantothenic acid, folic acid, niacin and riboflavin were found to be essential for the growth of *L. acidophilus* (Rogosa et al., 1981; Koser, 1988; Kandler and Weiss, 1986), however, Ledesma et al. (1977) reported that none of these vitamins was essential for the growth of *L. acidophilus*.

Rogosa et al. (1953) mentioned that riboflavin, folic acid, calcium pantothenate and niacin were essential, whereas pyridoxal or pyridoxamine showed stimulatory effect and thiamine, vitamin B12 and thymidine were not required for the growth of *L. casei*.

2.2.4 Fatty acids

Unsaturated fatty acids have been reported to stimulate the growth of *L. acidophilus*, whereas saturated fatty acids exert an inhibitory effect (Gyllenberg et al., 1956). Among unsaturated fatty acids, the requirement of oleic acid for this organism has been established (Hutchings and Boggiano, 1947).

2.2.5 Nucleic acid derivatives

Nucleic acid derivatives such as deoxyribosides of adenosine, adenine, thymine, guanine, cytosine, xanthine and hypoxanthine, deoxyriboside polyphosphate, uracil, deoxyuridine, 5-methyl pyrimidine 1,2 deoxyriboside were reported to be required for the growth of *L. acidophilus* (Reigh and Soska, 1967).

2.3 Acidophilus based products

Since acidophilus milk has very unattractive flavour and consistency, the acceptability of the product as such has been limited. In order to improve, it is desirable to develop acidophilus based products with improved palatability and taste. If this could be possible, then a product with both nutritional and therapeutic properties comparable to that of the acidophilus milk could be made available to a broader section of the consumers especially in developing world. A few such products which have already been developed are sweet acidophilus milk, acidophilus drink, acidophilus ice-cream and mixed culture yoghurt made with conventional yoghurt cultures and *L. acidophilus*.

2.3.1 Yogurt like product

In order to improve consumer acceptability of the yogurt from nutritional and therapeutic point of view, it was required to use the *L. bulgaricus* and *S. thermophilus* cultures along with the other suitable lactic acid producing cultures. Tramer (1973) suggested to use *L. acidophilus* as a optional additive culture of yogurt to increase its popularity. With this premise Aco-yoghurt was

developed in Switzerland (Spech, 1980). It is prepared by adding viable *L. acidophilus* to yoghurt prior to packaging so that the product contains $4-6 \times 10^7$ *L. acidophilus* per 200 milliliter. To prepare a more acceptable product, Vedamuthu (1974) suggested mixing of regular yoghurt and milk culture of *L. acidophilus* in a desired proportion and cooling the mixture quickly to 40°F or less followed by filling. He observed that the product thus prepared would have desired flavour, balance between yoghurt flora and *L. acidophilus*, and proportions of both the types of cultures could be maintained for at least a week. He advocated that it might be advertised as a speciality product and sold as such.

Gilliland and Speck (1977) found that *L. acidophilus* added to yoghurt decreased in numbers upon refrigerated storage. They observed that this instability was caused by compound(s) produced by *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* during its growth. Hydrogen peroxide produced by this organism during manufacture and/or storage was the main compound responsible for this effect since the added catalase reduced the antagonism. Earlier studies have also shown that *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* produced hydrogen peroxide in milk at 5°C in quantities sufficient to inhibit many bacteria (Premi and Battazzi, 1972; Gilliland and Speck, 1975). These findings suggest that yoghurt can not serve as an appropriate carrier for *L. acidophilus* since reasonable numbers of this organism will not survive considering the long periods for which this product is stored.

2.3.1.1 Starter culture activities

Greene, Geilman, and Cardwell (1990) compared the growth of *L. casei* (ATCC 393) on various media, included KF, MRS, Elliker, Rogosa SL and standard plate count Agar (SPC). They concluded that *L. casei* (ATCC 393) grew well on MRS, Elliker and Rogosa SL.

Lactobacillus casei was studied for its activity in skimmed milk of cow and buffalo. *L. casei* produced higher titratable and volatile acidities and had higher proteolytic activity in buffalo's milk than in cow's milk (Singh and Rangarathnan, 1979).

Savoyde Giori, Fontde Valdez, Ruiz Holgado and Oliver (1985) observed that *L. casei* (CRL 75, 200 and 238) showed no appreciable acid production at any of the temperature tested (10-50°C). In *L. casei* strains, the presence of pyruvate induced the production of neutral compounds (diacetyl and acetoin) and decreased the development of acidity. It was suggested that the

buffering effect of pyruvate at 22°C would allow a better proteolytic activity while a temperature of 45°C could be used in technological processes to obtain better quality products in shorter time (Benitode Cardenas and Peralde Portillo, 1992).

A slight reduction of total titratable acidity was observed when *L. casei* was incubated at 42°C rather than 30°C (Dutta, Kuila, Arora, Ranganathan, 1972; Singh, Ranganathan and Chander, 1980) whereas *L. acidophilus* was observed to produce more acidity and acetaldehyde at 42°C than 37°C (Singh, 1983). Vignolo, Pessedé-Ruiz-Holgado and Oliver (1988) observed that most of the strains of *L. casei* exhibited a maximum acid-producing rate at 30°C.

Toennies and Frank (1950) observed the maximum growth of *L. casei* 7568 at pH 6.35. Pilkhane (1977) also observed the maximum specific growth rate of *L. casei* ATCC 9460 at pH 6.3. Hood and Zottola (1988) suggested that selection for tolerance of low pH should be one of the selection criteria for *L. acidophilus* to be used in dietary foods.

L. casei was tested for its ability to grow in *Lactobacillus* broth (LB) containing 0.0, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25 and 0.3 % bile salts. After incubation for 4 days at 37°C bacterial counts were 184, 185, 155, 123 and 85 /ml (Khattab, Abou-Donia and Donia, 1987). Fetlinski and Stepaniak (1891) determined the resistance of selected *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus* strains to bile salts and observed the differences between species of *Lactobacillus* and strains in resistance to bile salts.

2.3.1.2 Nutritional attributes

Conversion of constituents of whole milk cultured by *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* at 37°C for 24 h was studied. Culturing with *L. acidophilus* increased soluble N compounds and free amino acids, while culturing with *L. casei* had no effect on soluble N compounds and decreased free amino acids (Gon, Kwon, Ahn and Yoon, 1988).

Manufacture of liquid yoghurt using culture of *L. casei* YIT 9018 was studied in a test in which reconstituted dried skim milk + 2 % glucose was inoculated with *L. casei* at 10⁸ cells/ml and incubated at 37°C for 144 h. Maximum log count, reached after 48 h, and final log count were 9.87 and 9.27 /ml. During incubation glucose concentration decreased from 2.25 to 0.25 %, lactose decreased from 7.10 to 6.45 % and free tyrosine increased from 0.064 to 0.195 mg/ml (Yoon, Paik, Lee and Yoon, 1982).

Lactose utilization by *L. casei* was observed maximum at temperature between 40 and 50°C and was not greatly affected by pH 4.5-5.5; pH 5.5 and temperature 43°C were chosen as optimum. A lactose concentration of 4.5 % w/v gave the highest lactic acid concentration. Lactic acid production was improved by Mn²⁺ and mustard oilmeal. Under these conditions, 3.1 % lactic acid, 93.8 % lactose utilization and an hourly productivity of 0.64 g/l were obtained at 43°C for 48 h (Tuli, Sethi, Khanna, Marwaha and Kennedy, 1985).

Lactose-hydrolysing enzyme of *L. acidophilus* was identified as beta-galactosidase. Maximum activity occurred when it was incubated with Mg²⁺ and mercaptoethanol in sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) at 37°C. Lactose and galactose both induced enzyme activity but glucose did not. Phospho-beta-galactosidase activity was not detected (Nielsen, 1987; Nielsen and Gilliland, 1992). Sontakke, Dane and Sannabhadti, (1990) detected lactase activity in *L. acidophilus* LBKV3 but not in *L. casei* LBKI-4, DM-22A and DM-4A. *L. acidophilus* degraded 80 % of total lactose during incubation for 72 h and showed lactase activity comparable to that of yoghurt bacteria when assayed individually but not when grown in association.

Lactic acid bacteria form differing amounts of acetaldehyde during the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins and nucleic acids. The degree to which acetaldehyde accumulates in growth medium depends on whether or not the organism has enzymes which convert this compound to other metabolites, principally ethanol. Phosphotransacetylase, acetate kinase, aldehyde dehydrogenase and 2-deoxyriboaldolase activities were found in *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus*. Alpha-carboxylase and threonine aldolase activities only occurred in *L. acidophilus*. In contrast, phosphoketolase activity was present in *L. casei* but absent in *L. acidophilus*. The accumulation of acetaldehyde in the growth medium is possible because the activities of enzymes which catalyse the formation of acetaldehyde are higher than those of enzymes which convert it to ethanol (Gonzalez, Moratade-Ambrosine, Mancade-Nadra, Oliver, Ambrsini, Nadra, 1994).

Elsadek, Naguib and Negm (1972) determined acetaldehyde and diacetyl production in autoclaved skim milk for pure cultures of *Lactobacilli*, streptococci and yeast. *L. bulgaricus* produced more acetaldehyde (3.3-17 ppm) than *L. casei* (2.7-3.6 ppm). Singh (1983) observed that *L. acidophilus* produced more acetaldehyde at 42°C than at 37°C.

2.3.1.3 Therapeutic attributes

Acidophilus based products are known widely more for its possible therapeutic values than for its flavour and other attributes. The use of this fermented milk as a therapeutic agent is based on the assumption that this formulation combats the so called auto-intoxications caused by accumulation in the body, of toxic substances elaborated by the growth of certain toxigenic bacteria. In addition to this, the constant use of acidophilus milk is recommended for controlling several other intestinal disorders. The proper use of acidophilus milk in several feeding trails substantiated the beneficial effect of this product in patients suffering from simple constipation, constipation accompanied by biliary symptoms, so-called “mucous-colitis” or irritable colon and colonic ulcerative colitis.

Lactobacillus acidophilus is considered as a normal inhabitant of the intestinal tract and acidophilus based product have been considered as practical means of bringing about a predominance of *L. acidophilus* in the small intestine. However, not all strains of *L. acidophilus* can be established with equal success in the intestinal tract of man (Gilliland et al., 1978; Hargrove and Alford, 1978; Gilliland et al., 1989; Gilliland and Walker, 1980). Since the therapeutic value of acidophilus based product is dependent upon the implantation of viable *L. acidophilus*, it is prescribed to use acidophilus based products regularly along with suitable carbohydrate such as lactose or dextran. These carbohydrates are effective as they are absorbed from the tract fairly slowly, thus remaining available longer in the intestine as food for the *Lactobacilli*. The ability of *L. acidophilus* to grow at low surface tension may account for its implantation in the gastro-intestinal tract, whereas closely related species can not grow there.

Lactobacilli, primarily *L. acidophilus* occur in vagina from puberty to menopause (Lock et al., 1848; Butler and Beakley, 1960; Rogosa and Sharpe, 1980; Wylie and Henderson, 1969) and contribute to maintenance of acidic pH through fermentation of carbohydrates particularly glycogen (Whlie and Henderson, 1969; Hurley et al., 1974). Administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics suppresses the *Lactobacilli* (Huppert et al., 1955) which results in disturbance of ecological balance in vagina. Under such conditions yeast infections (monilia vaginitis) occur which cause irritation and inflammation of vaginal canal. These infections are caused primarily by *Candida albicans*. Guillot (1958) reported that *L. acidophilus* produced an inhibitor which was found to be active against *Candida albicans*.

Besides these possible benefits from consuming acidophilus based products, control of serum cholesterol and antagonistic effects have gained greater attention of investigators, therefore in the present review greater attention has been focussed on these benefits.

2.3.1.3.1 Control of serum cholesterol

Hypocholestermia predisposes cardiac disease in humans (Lipid Research Clinics Programm, 1984). Therefore various attempts have been made to reduce cholesterol levels by consumption of certain cultured dairy products (Mann, 1977; Hephher et al., 1979). The intestinal microflora influenced cholesterol absorption as indicated by Byseen (1973) who showed that conventional animals excreted more amount of cholesterol in their faeces than did germ-free animals.

Mann and Spoerry (1974) found that consumption of milk fermented with a *Lactobacillus* strain decreased serum cholesterol levels in man, possibly due to production of a factor, which impaired cholesterol synthesis. Harrison and Peat (1975) investigated that the decreased serum cholesterol level was associated with the increased number of *Lactobacilli* in faeces of infants, when they were fed *L. acidophilus* containing formula.

Gilliland et al. (1985) observed considerable variation among *L. acidophilus* strains isolated from faeces of pigs with regard to their ability to grow in presence of bile and their cholesterol uptake from the growth medium.

The uptake of cholesterol occurred only when the culture was growing in the presence of bile salts under anaerobic conditions. Further, they indicated that certain strains of *L. acidophilus* might act directly on cholesterol in gastrointestinal tract and thus might be useful in reducing serum cholesterol levels. However, Gilliland and Walker (1990) did not observed any direct relationship between bile tolerance and cholesterol assimilation among the *L. acidophilus* strains tested.

Certain strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* possess the ability to deconjugate bile salts (Gilliland and Speck, 1977). This deconjugation activity assumes significance in relation to serum cholesterol levels when it is considered that deconjugated bile acids function more poorly in supporting absorption of lipids from the intestinal tract than do conjugated ones (Gyssen, 1973; Gilliland, 1989).

2.3.1.3.2 Antagonistic characteristics

Lactobacilli are normal inhabitants of the intestinal tract of humans (Haenel, 1970; Gilliland et al., 1975; Gilliland, 1979; Sandine, 1979). In the gut ecosystem it is not always the number of a particular bacterial species that is important but also its type. *L. casei* or *L. acidophilus* even with a very low number influences the growth and activities of other intestinal microbes, which are present in higher concentrations. Thus one of the beneficial functions of *L. casei* or *L. acidophilus* in the intestine is to maintain a desirable ecology by controlling excessive growth of undesirable and transient microorganisms including pathogens. Many conditions such as abusive and improper dietary habits, starvation, alcohol consumption, stress, diseases of the digestive tract, oral antibiotic therapy and surgical operations eliminate or considerably reduce the population of *L. acidophilus* in the intestine of the host (Mital and Garg, 1992). This in turn gives rise to intestinal maladies including diarrhoea, flatulence and infection by enteric pathogens.

Kivanc (1990) assessed antibacterial properties of cell free filtrate from *L. casei* against 10 pathogenic bacteria. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the least sensitive of the tested pathogens, followed by *E. coli* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* was the most sensitive.

Molechanova (1968) observed that certain strains of *L. casei* displayed strong bactericidal properties, apparent within 24-48 h, against *Shigella flexneri*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium*. Grinevich and Makarova (1974) examined various strains of *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus* for their antagonistic activities against organism causing cholera, dysentery, paratyphoid and typhoid.

Several investigators have shown that *L. acidophilus* exerts inhibitory action against commonly known intestinal and food-borne pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Mikolajcik and Hamdan, 1975; Gilliland and Speck, 1977; Hosono et al., 1977; Mehta et al., 1983; Prasad and Gandhi, 1987).

Lortie, Simard and Lavoie (1992) studied the characteristics of inhibitory substances produced by different strains of *L. casei* against different species of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The inhibitory agents produced under anaerobic conditions were resistant to proteolytic

enzymes and heat treatment (121°C for 20 min). It was concluded that produced lactic acid was mainly responsible for inhibition.

L. casei var. rhamnosus GR-1 and *L. acidophilus* 76 were found to exert an inhibitory effect on pyelonephritogenic mutant *E. coli* Hu734 and *E. coli* ATCC 25922. The bioactivity of the inhibitor, produced was retained under pH buffered conditions and was bactericidal. The bioactive substance was heat labile, was not precipitated by up to 80 % ammonium sulphate and was extractable in chloroform. It was concluded that inhibitor was not lactic acid or hydrogen peroxide (McGroarty and Reid 1988).

Growth inhibitor effects of culture supernatants of *L. casei* were measured against different pathogens. All the test pathogens were inhibited by whole culture or culture supernatants of *L. casei* but not by a cell suspension of *L. casei* or the neutralized culture supernatant. The antibacterial activity of the *L. casei* culture appears to be mainly due to acid formation and possibly by production of small amounts of antibiotics and peroxide (Choi, Chung and Yong, 1984).

Vignolo, Suriani and Oliner (1993) observed that the substance excreted by *L. casei* CRL 705 was active against a wide range of Gram-negative bacteria. The activity of this substance was inactivated by papain, trypsin and pepsin, but was resistant to heat at 100°C for 20 minutes. The substance was characterized as bacteriocin and it was termed as Lactocin 705. Whereas Lortie, Simard and Lavoie (1993) demonstrated that inhibitory substances produced by different strains of *L. casei* were not bacteriocins, since they were resistant to the proteolytic activity of papain, chymotrypsin and pronase E. It was concluded that antibiotics, peptides, short-chain fatty acids and lactic acid were responsible for antimicrobial effects.

The antibiotic-like substances produced by various strains of *L. acidophilus* were designated as lactocidin (Vincent, 1959), acidolin (Sabine, 1963) and acidophilin (Shahani et al. 1977). Vervaeck, Huyghebaert, Moor, Mey and DeMoor (1990) characterized the inhibitory substance as protein in nature. The activity of substance was not affected by heating at 100°C for 1 h and higher activity was obtained in pH-stat (pH 6) than in non-pH stat fermentation at 37°C.

The exact mechanism whereby *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus* extracts antagonistic action against pathogens is not completely understood. *L. casei* and *L. acidophilus* produce number of

compounds possessing antimicrobial activity. Those include organic acids such as lactic acid, acetic acid, H₂O₂ and antibiotic like substances. Presumably combined effect of all these factors is responsible for antagonistic activity of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei*.

In addition, *L. acidophilus* has been reported to produce bacteriocin(s) (deKlerk and Coetzee, 1961; Barefoot and Klaenhammer, 1984; Ferreira and Gilliland, 1988). Barefoot and Klaenhammer (1983) examined 52 strains of *L. acidophilus* and detected three distinct bacteriocin type activities. Therefore, the capability of an organism to produce multiple bacteriocins needs further investigation. By definition, bacteriocins are active against closely related bacterial species. Therefore, bacteriocins may not be of much help in controlling intestinal pathogens. However, they may play an important role in inhibiting other *Lactobacilli* and related organisms and thus enabling selected strains of *L. acidophilus* to establish in the complex ecosystem of the gut. *L. acidophilus* apparently is capable of producing more than one inhibitory system and the antagonistic action they exert towards intestinal pathogens likely results from the involvement of more than one particular inhibitor (Gilliland, 1989). Since variations occur among different strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei*, it is most likely that one strain may not produce all the inhibitory compounds attributed to these organisms.

2.3.1.4 Quality and Sensory characteristics

Shin, Lee, Kin and Back (1991) examined changes in quality and sensory evaluation to select the best index for estimating the quality of stirred yoghurt stored at different temperatures. The results obtained were as follows. (1) The initial taste of the stirred yoghurt was maintained during storage for 16 days at 5°C. There was a difference between initial taste and the taste after storage for 14 days at 10°C, 6 days at 15°C and 4 days at 20°C, (2) The higher the storage temperature of stirred yoghurt the faster were the rates of changes of titratable acidity, pH and viable cells of lactic acid bacteria. In particular, the number of viable cells of lactic acid bacteria was maintained at $> 10^8$ c.f.u./ml during 16 days at 5, 10 and 15°C but decreased to $< 10^8$ c.v.u./ml after 14 days at 20°C and 6 days at 30°C (3). The correlation between taste and flavour, taste and pH, and taste and viable cells of lactic acid bacteria were positive with high significance ($P < 0.005$), but the correlations between taste and sourness, and taste and titratable acidity were negative with high significance ($P < 0.005$). The pH of the stirred yoghurt was selected as a quality index for taste.

Studies were conducted on the changes of the physical properties and the shelf-life of liquid yogurt stored at different temperatures. The correlations coefficient between sensory evaluation and physical properties were examined, correlation coefficient between taste and viable cells of lactic acid bacteria showed the highest positive value ($P < 0.005$) at all storage temperatures. Therefore, viable cells of lactic acid bacteria were selected as an index quality attribute for taste during storage (Lee, Kim, Shin and Back, 1991).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Milk

Fresh cow and buffalo milk obtained from the Livestock Research Centre of the University, skimmed in the Dairy processing plant, Department of Food Science and Technology was used in the study.

3.2 Cultures

The freeze dried cultures of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-I and 301 strains, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*, *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* were obtained from National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal (India). The above cultures were activated in Lactic broth at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and then maintained in sterilized litmus milk by fortnightly transfers and stored at 5°C between transfers. The cultures were subcultured 3-4 times for activation before use.

Pathogenic organisms *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi* were obtained from Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar (India).

3.3 Media

Elliker broth obtained from HiMedia Laboratories (P) Limited, Bombay, was used. The medium was reconstituted as per the instructions of the manufacturer.

3.4 Litmus milk

Litmus solution (3 % w/v) was added to skimmed milk @ 7 %(v/v) and the litmus milk was sterilized at 15 psi for 10 minutes and then used for maintaining the cultures.

3.5 Chemicals

Analyticals reagent (A.R.) grade chemicals were used in this study.

3.6 Analytical determinations

3.6.1 Titratable acidity and pH

Titrate acidity of the samples was determined by potentiometric method as described in International IDF standard (1991). A test proportion (10 g) of sample was suspended in water (10 ml) and titrated by 0.1 mol/lit NaOH to pH 8.3 (phenolphthalein indicator was used in titration) and the volume of NaOH (in ml) was multiplied by 0.9 and divided by the mass (in g) of test proportion to give the lactic acid content in g/100 g.

Changes in pH were measured using EC digital pH meter (model no. pH 5652, make - E.C.I. New Delhi).

3.6.2 Lactose utilization

Modified Lane and Eynon method as described by Ranganna (1986) was used to estimate lactose content in the samples. Ten grams of the sample was deproteinized by adding 20 ml of 2.7 % barium hydroxide solution slowly with agitation followed by 20 ml of 5% zinc sulphate solution. The contents were allowed to stand for 10 min and then transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. After making up the volume to 100 ml with distilled water, the contents were filtered through Whatman No. 4 filter paper. The supernatant thus obtained was used to determine lactose content by titrating against Fehling's solution using methylene blue as the indicator.

The lactose content in the sample was calculated according to the following expression.

$$\% \text{ Lactose} = \frac{[(\text{mg of invert sugar} \times \text{Dilution}) / (\text{Titre value} \times \text{wt of sample} \times 1000)] \times 100}{1}$$

Where, mg of invert sugar represents the factor for Fehling's solution.

Standard solution of lactose (2.5 mg/ml) was used to determine factors for Fehling's solution. The accuracy of method under the experimental conditions was tested.

Per cent lactose utilization was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Lactose utilization} = \frac{[(\text{Initial lactose content} - \text{Residual lactose at test hour}) / \text{Initial lactose content}] \times 100}{1}$$

3.6.3 Fat

Fat content in the samples was determined by Soxhlet Extraction Method (AOAC, 1975). Ten grams of sample was dried at 100°C for 3 h and extracted for 16-18 h with petroleum ether (B.P. 40-60°C). Thereafter, the ether was evaporated and the extracted fat was weighed.

3.6.4 Moisture

Moisture content in the samples was determined by AOAC (1975) procedure. The sample (10 g) was weighed and dried at 100°C for 3 h until a constant weight. The loss in weight was calculated to determine moisture content.

3.6.5 Ash

Ash content in the samples was determined according to AOAC (1975) method. The sample (10 g) was weighed into a silica dish, charred and ignited in muffle furnace at 550°C until ash was carbon free. The dish was cooled in a dessicator and weighed.

3.6.6 Protein

Kjeldhal method as described by AOAC (1975) was used to determine nitrogen in the samples which was multiplied by the factor of 6.38 to calculate the protein content.

3.6.7 Soluble nitrogen

The soluble nitrogen in the samples was estimated according to Kosikowski (1966). The sample (5 g) was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask followed by a small amount of Sharp's extraction solution (tempered to 40°C) and the content was mixed. Later on, more Sharp's solution was added to make a dilute suspension and the volume was made up to 100 ml with glass distilled water. Thereafter, the flask was kept in a water bath at 50°C for 1 h with occasional shaking. The contents were filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The filtrate (25 ml) was transferred to a 300 ml Kjeldahl flask, digested, distilled and titrated to determine nitrogen. The soluble nitrogen was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ soluble nitrogen} = [14 \times (V-B) \times N \times 100] / W$$

where,

V = Volume of HCl used for sample,

B = Volume of HCl used for blank,

N = Normality of HCl,

W = Weight of the aliquot in mg

The composition of reagent was as under :

Stock A : 57.5 ml glacial acetic acid; 47.0 g sodium chloride; 136.1 g sodium acetate; 8.9 g calcium chloride. All the constituents were dissolved in glass distilled water and the final volume was made up to 1 litre.

Sharp's extraction solution: 250 ml of Stock 'A' was diluted to 1 litre in glass distilled water.

3.6.8 Acetaldehyde

Acetaldehyde content in the samples was estimated according to Robinson et al. (1977). The sample (50 g) was weighed in a 500 ml beaker and mixed with approximately 100 ml of glass distilled water. The contents were then transferred with careful rinsing to a 250 ml volumetric flask, and shaken thoroughly but gently. Twenty ml of 5% zinc sulphate solution was then added, followed by 20 ml of 0.3 M barium hydroxide. Thereafter, the volume was made up to 250 ml and the contents were centrifuged at 1000 x g for 5 min. One millilitre of magenta solution (0.04 % basic fuchsin in 2 % sulphuric acid) was added to appropriate aliquot (4 ml) of the supernatant thus obtained and the contents were shaken gently. Sodium sulphite solution (1.0 ml) was then added and the mixture was allowed to stand in the dark for 25 min. The colour intensity of the mixture was measured at 560 nm using reagent blank prepared in the same manner as the experimental without the sample. The acetaldehyde content in the samples was determined using standard curve and expressed as parts per million (ppm). The standard curve was prepared by the same procedure followed for experimental samples using 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 µg concentration of acetaldehyde.

For preparing sodium sulphite solution, anhydrous 0.354 sodium sulphite was added to an aliquot of solution containing 2.72 g mercuric chloride and 1.17 g sodium chloride per 100 ml glass distilled water. Once sodium sulphite was dissolved, the volume was made up to 100 ml with remaining mercuric chloride-sodium chloride solution.

3.6.9 Viable count

Viable count in the samples were determined according to APHA (1972) procedure using Lactic agar (Elliker et al. 1956). Appropriate dilutions were prepared using 9 ml dilution blanks and plated in duplicate.

3.6.10 Generation time

Viable counts were plotted on semi-logarithmic paper against time in hours. Generation time of the organisms was calculated as described by Stanier et al. (1987).

$$\log_{10}N - \log_{10}N_0 = (k / 2.303) \times (t - t_0) \dots \dots \dots 1$$

where, k is the exponential growth rate constant and is defined as number of doubling per unit time and the values of N and N₀ are the number of cells/ml at time, t and t₀, respectively. Generation time (g) is defined as the time in which all the components of the culture increase by a factor of 2. the relation between g and k can be derived from eq. 1. If the time interval considered (t-t₀) is equal to g, then N would be twice no. Substituting these we have,

$$g = 0.693 / k \dots \dots \dots 2$$

3.7 Characterization of strains

3.7.1 Selection of strains

The strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei* and their combination were selected, on the basis of developed titratable acidity in cow and buffalo skim milk after 16 hrs incubation at 37°C using 1 % rate of inoculum. Strains and combination producing maximum titratable acidity were selected.

3.7.2 Effect of type of milk

Effect of type of milk investigated using cow and buffalo skim milk.

3.7.3 Effect of fat content

Cow milk was adjusted to 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 5.0 and 7.0 per cent fat to study its effect on the growth of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-I, *Lactobacillus casei*-RTS and their combination. The test medium

was inoculated with activated culture @ 1 % and incubated at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16-18 hrs. The growth of the cultures was evaluated by measuring the increase in titratable acidity and plotted against fat content.

3.7.4 Effect of sugar

Skim cow milk was adjusted to sucrose 0.0, 3.0, 5.0, 7.0 and 9.0 per cent to study its effect on the growth of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-I, *Lactobacillus casei*-RTS and their associative growth. The test medium was inoculated with activated culture @ 1 % and incubated at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16-18 h. The growth of the cultures was determined by measuring the increase in titratable acidity and plotted against sugar content.

3.7.5 Effect of inoculum rate

Inoculum of activated cultures of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS was used @ 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 per cent to study its effect on titratable acidity. The inoculated test medium was incubated at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16-18 hrs and the developed titratable acidity was plotted against inoculum rate.

3.7.6 Effect of incubation temperature

To study the effect of incubation temperature on the growth of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-I, *Lactobacillus casei*-RTS and their associative growth, autoclaved cow skim milk was used. The autoclaved skim cow milk was inoculated with activated culture @ 1% and incubated at 30, 37, 42 and 50°C temperatures. The growth of the cultures was determined by measuring the increase in titratable acidity and plotted against incubation temperature.

3.7.7 Effect of total solids

Fresh skim milk of cow was supplemented with 2.0, 3.0 and 5.0 per cent skim milk powder to study its effect on the growth of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS. The test medium was inoculated @ 1 % and incubated at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16-18 hrs. The growth was determined by measuring increase in titratable acidity.

3.7.8 Effect of pH and bile salt concentration

Elliker broth was adjusted to pH 4.0, 5.0, 6.0 and 6.9 with sterile 1.0 N hydrochloric acid to study the effect of low pH on growth and survival of different *Lactobacillus casei* strains. The

test medium was inoculated with activated culture @ 1% and incubated at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The growth of the cultures was determined by measuring the increase in optical density at 620 nm and plotted against time.

Survival studies in presence of bile salts, according to the procedure described by Gilliland and Walker (1990), were conducted using *Lactobacillus casei*-RTS and *Lactobacillus casei*-300. The level of bile salt (Sodium glycolate) tested was 0.3% (W/V). Elliker broth with or without added bile salt was inoculated with activated test culture @ 1% (cell density $4-8 \times 10^8/\text{ml}$) and incubated at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Bacterial growth was determined by measuring the increase in optical density (OD) at 620 nm at 0, 4, 8, 12 and 16 h using digital spectrophotometer, Model 106 (Systronics, Ahmedabad, India).

3.7.9 Cholesterol uptake

Lactobacillus casei strains were tested for their hypocholesterolemic activity according to the procedure described by Gilliland and Walker (1990).

Elliker broth (Elliker et al., 1956) supplemented with 0.2% sodium thioglycolate or 0.3% bile salt was prepared and sterilized at 121°C for 15 min. Following cooling, pleuropneumonia-like organism (PPLO) serum was added equal to 10 % of broth and mixed thoroughly. Thereafter, the broth containing PPLO serum was aseptically dispensed (8 ml/tube) into sterile screw-cap test tubes. The tubes were then inoculated with active broth culture of the test organism @ 1% and incubated at 37°C in a water bath. The control consisted of uninoculated tubes. At the end of 16-18 h, the cells were harvested by centrifugation ($12,000 \times g$) at $2 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min and the cell pellet thus obtained was resuspended in distilled water to the original volume of the broth culture.

O-Phthalaldehyde method as described by Rudel and Morris (1973) was used to determine cholesterol in spent broth, resuspended cells and the control. A 0.5 ml aliquot of the sample was transferred to clean test tube (duplicates for each sample). Thereafter, 3 ml of 95% ethanol was added, followed by 2 ml of 50% potassium hydroxide and the contents were mixed thoroughly. The experimental tubes were then heated for 10 min in a water bath maintained at 60°C and after cooling, 5 ml hexane was dispensed into each tube. The contents were mixed thoroughly using a vortex mixer. Thereafter 3 ml of distilled water was added and the mixing was repeated. The tubes were allowed to stand for 15 min at room temperature to permit phase separation. Then 2.5

ml of the hexane layer was transferred into a clean test tube. The hexane was evaporated from each tubes at 80°C under vacuum. O-Phthalaldehyde reagent (4 ml) was then added to each test tube. The reagent contained 0.5 mg. O-phthalaldehyde per ml glacial acetic acid. The tubes were allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 min and then 2 ml concentrated sulphuric acid was pipetted slowly down the side of each tube. The contents of each tube were immediately mixed thoroughly using vortex mixer. After standing at room temperature for an additional 10 min the optical density was read at 550 nm using reagent blank. The reagent blank consisted of the sample tubes treated as above but without addition of PPLO serum. The concentration of cholesterol in the samples was determined using standard curve and expressed as micrograms cholesterol per millilitre. The standard curve was drawn using the same procedure with the exception that assays were done using : 0,10,20,30,40 and 50 mg in place of sample. The OD values thus obtained were plotted against cholesterol concentration in micrograms.

3.7.10 Antagonistic activity against different pathogens

Lactobacillus acidophilus strain I, and *Lactobacillus casei* strain RTS were tested for antagonistic activity in milk culture filtrates and by their ability to inhibit growth of different intestinal and food-borne pathogens in associative cultures.

3.7.10.1 Preparation of milk culture filtrate

Sterilized milk (200 ml) was inoculated with active culture of test organism @ 2.5% and incubated at 37°C for 48 h. At the end of incubation the curdled milk was centrifuged at 2000 × g for 20 min at 4°C and the culture filtrate thus obtained was filtered using 0.45 µm membrane filter. The culture filtrate was then tested for inhibitory activity against different pathogens by modified agar well assay technique (BSI, 1968).

3.7.10.2 Activity against different pathogens

Seeded plates were prepared by transferring 0.2 ml of active culture (OD 0.45 - 0.55) of the desired pathogens and then layering with 20 ml of Mueller Hinton molten agar (45°C). The contents were mixed gently by rotating the plates clockwise and anticlockwise. After solidification the plates were kept at 37°C for 2 h and were punched aseptically using sterile well cutter. A 0.2 ml aliquot of culture filtrate obtained from test organism was poured into each well aseptically. Thereafter, the plates were kept at 4°C for 2 h and then incubated at 37°C for 24-36 h.

At the end of incubation period the diameter of the zone surrounding the well, if any, was measured using Vernier calipers.

3.7.11 Growth

The growth of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS was determined using the following parameters.

- a. viable count
- b. % titratable acidity
- c. pH
- d. lactose utilization
- e. soluble nitrogen
- f. acetaldehyde production

These parameters were determined in standardized milk after 0, 4, 8, 12 and 16 hrs of incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, using inoculum of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination @ 3 % (1:1).

3.8 Product preparation

3.8.1 Preparation of regular yoghurt

Sch.dgr. 3.8.1: Preparation of regular yoghurt

3.8.2 Preparation of yoghurt like product

Yoghurt like product was manufactured in the same manner as regular yoghurt using the starter culture of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS @ 3 % (1:1).

3.9 Product evaluation

3.9.1 Sensory evaluation

Freshly prepared yoghurt like product and regular yoghurt samples were evaluated for detectable differences in taste, flavour, texture and overall acceptability on a nine point hedonic scale as described by Larmond (1977). The taste panel consisted of 20 semi trained panelist.

3.9.2 Storage studies

The final products were kept for comparative storage studies at $5\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 9 days in sterilized 100 ml cups. The samples were comparatively evaluated for sensory and biochemical characteristics after 0, 3, 6 and 9 days of storage.

3.10 Statistical analysis

Procedure for statistical analysis as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1968) were used to analyze the data for mean, standard deviation, regression and least significant difference among treatments.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present investigation envisaged to select strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei* to manufacture yogurt like product. The selected strains were studied for growth characteristics and biochemical changes to optimize the level of fat, total solids, sugar and incubation temperature. These strains were also examined for bile tolerance, Hypocholesterolic effect, survival at different pH, lactose utilization, therapeutic attributes and antagonistic activities. The yoghurt like product thus prepared using the selected strains and optimized level of growth requirements, was evaluated for sensory, biochemical and microbiological characteristics and compared with regular yogurt. The results obtained are presented as below.

4.1 Effect of type of milk on per cent titratable acidity

The growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. acidophilus*-301, *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 were studied using cow and buffalo skim milk. The per cent titratable acidity of cow and buffalo skim milk inoculated with tested strains *L. acidophilus*-301 and I at the end of 16 hrs were 0.95 ± 0.04 , 1.14 ± 0.05 and 1.07 ± 0.05 , 1.21 ± 0.04 , respectively. The changes in pH were more or less same in conformity with titratable acidity production data. At the end of 16 h, the pH of cow and buffalo skim milk inoculated with *L. acidophilus*-I and 301 were 4.06 ± 0.09 , 4.32 ± 0.11 and 3.96 ± 0.09 , 4.15 ± 0.13 , respectively.

Table 4.1: Effect of different strains of L. acidophilus and L. casei on titratable acidity and pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$

Strain	Cow skim milk % TA	Cow skim milk pH	Buffalo skim milk % TA	Buffalo skim +milk pH
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I	1.14 ± 0.05	4.06 ± 0.09	1.21 ± 0.04	3.96 ± 0.09
<i>L. acidophilus</i> - 301	0.95 ± 0.04	4.32 ± 0.11	1.07 ± 0.05	4.15 ± 0.13
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS	0.37 ± 0.03	5.63 ± 0.07	0.42 ± 0.02	5.54 ± 0.10

Strain	Cow skim milk % TA	Cow skim milk pH	Buffalo skim milk % TA	Buffalo skim +milk pH
<i>L. casei</i> -300	0.32±0.01	5.73±0.20	0.38±0.01	5.65±0.30

1. All values are expressed as mean + Sd of six replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial pH and % TA of sterilized skim milk were 6.5 ± 0.10 and 0.19 ± 0.02 , respectively.
4. Statistical analysis for significant difference between strains - CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.04093.
5. Statistical analysis for significant difference between cow and buffalo milk - CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.02894.

Table 4.2: Effect of different strains of *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* in combinations on titratable acidity and pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during incubation at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Strain	Cow skim milk % TA	Cow skim milk pH	Buffalo skim milk % TA	Buffalo skim milk pH
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	1.27±0.11	3.89±0.12	1.35±0.06	3.84±0.08
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I + <i>L. casei</i> -300	1.24±0.03	3.92±0.07	1.34±0.07	3.85±0.11
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -301 + <i>L. casei</i> - RTS	1.12±0.09	4.12±0.13	1.18±0.08	3.98±0.18
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -301 + <i>L. casei</i> -300	1.04±0.07	4.18±0.05	1.08±0.05	4.15±0.07

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of six replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial pH and % TA of sterilized skim milk were 6.5 ± 0.10 and 0.18 ± 0.02 , respectively.
4. Statistical analysis for significant difference between strains - CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0663.
5. Statistical analysis for significant difference between cow and buffalo milk - CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0493.

Figure 4.1: Effect of different strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei* on titratable acidity of cow and buffalo skim milk during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.2: Effect of different strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei* on pH of cow and buffalo skim milk during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

The per cent titratable acidity of cow and buffalo skim milk inoculated with *L. casei*-300 and RTS strains at the end of 16 h were 0.32 ± 0.01 , 0.37 ± 0.03 and 0.38 ± 0.01 , 0.42 ± 0.02 , respectively, corresponding pH were 5.73 ± 0.20 , 5.63 ± 0.07 and 5.65 ± 0.30 , 5.54 ± 0.10 (Table 4.1 and Fig. 4.1). It is clear from Table 4.1 and Fig. 4.1 that among the tested strains, *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS produced maximum lactic acid in buffalo skim milk.

Effect of different strains in combination on titratable acidity and pH of cow and buffalo skim milk were studied and shown in Table 4.2. Different combinations, *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS; *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-300; *L. acidophilus*-301 and *L. casei*-RTS; *L. acidophilus*-301 and *L. casei*-300, at the end of 16 h, produced titratable acidity 1.27 ± 0.11 ; 1.24 ± 0.03 ; 1.12 ± 0.09 ; 1.04 ± 0.07 and 1.35 ± 0.06 ; 1.34 ± 0.07 ; 1.18 ± 0.08 ; 1.08 ± 0.05 in cow and buffalo skim milk, respectively, corresponding pH of the cow and buffalo skim milk inoculated with these combinations were 3.89 ± 0.12 ; 3.92 ± 0.07 ; 4.12 ± 0.13 ; 4.18 ± 0.05 and 3.84 ± 0.08 ; 3.85 ± 0.11 ; 3.98 ± 0.16 ; 4.15 ± 0.07 , respectively. Among the different combinations, *L. acidophilus*-I with *L. casei*-RTS produced maximum titratable acidity in buffalo as well as in cow skim milk (Table 4.2 and Fig. 4.2).

On the basis of above observations the strains of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination were selected for further studies.

Research conducted during last decade have greatly enhanced our understanding about the health promoting properties of the products, prepared by using lactic acid bacteria (Gilliland, 1978; Sandine, 1979; Speck, 1980; Nashisi, 1986). Therefore in present investigation, lactic acid production was taken as main parameter. The cultures developed significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher acidity in buffalo milk. Thomas, Nambudripad and Dudani (1968) showed that rate of acid production by lactic cultures was comparatively higher in buffalo milk than in cow milk. A significant difference in acid production by lactic cultures in cow and buffalo milk has been also reported by Singh and Ranganathan (1979). The selection of strains on the basis of higher acid production as done in present investigation is also supported by Vedamuthu (1974). He has supported that selection of strains is usually based on their ability to produce acid at faster rate. Statistical analysis showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in production of lactic acid among

strains and type of milk. Among cow and buffalo milk, critical difference at 5 % level of significance is only 0.0493, hence cow milk was selected for further trials.

4.2 Effect of fat levels on acid production

The effect of fat on titratable acidity of cow milk with strains of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination after 16 hours of incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ is shown in Table 4.3 and Fig. 4.3. Significant reduction in acid production was observed from all the tested strains irrespective of increased fat per cent in milk samples from 1.0 to 7.0 per cent. The per cent titratable acidity for *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination at the end of 16 h were 0.92 ± 0.06 , 0.25 ± 0.04 and 0.86 ± 0.03 , respectively, at 7.0 per cent fat, as compared to 1.14 ± 0.05 , 0.39 ± 0.02 and 1.23 ± 0.08 at 1.0 per cent level.

Table 4.3: Effect of fat levels on titratable acidity of cow milk using *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Strain	1 %	2 %	3 %	5 %	7 %
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^a	1.14 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.07	1.02 ± 0.05	0.90 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.06
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS ^b	0.39 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.04	0.29 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.04
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^c + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	1.23 ± 0.08	1.07 ± 0.07	1.10 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.03

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of six replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial pH and % TA of sterilized milk were 6.5 ± 0.10 and 0.18 ± 0.02 , respectively.
4. The values in different rows differ significantly.

^aCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0784.

^bCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0517.

^cCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.1195.

Figure 4.3: Effect of different fat levels on titratable acidity of cow milk, using *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$

Results of this investigation showed that the growth of *L. acidophilus*-I and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) at all the levels of fat per cent used except at 2.0 and 3.0 per cent in milk with CD 0.0794 and 0.1195, respectively at 5 % level of significance whereas no significant difference in the growth of *L. casei*-RTS was observed in milk containing 1.0, 2.0 or 3.0 per cent fat (CD at 5 % level of significance was 0.0517). On the basis of these observations, cow milk standardized to 2 per cent fat was selected to manufacture yoghurt like product. The selection of 2 % fat in milk is also supported by the results of Cottennie (1978), who reported that most of the yoghurt manufactured in Europe have 1-3 % fat and he also stressed on the importance of fat in relation to both consistency and flavour. In addition to above, much emphasis is being given to low fat milk product for health conscious people, specially persons suffering from coronary problems.

4.3 Effect of sugar on acid production

The effect of sugar addition to milk on per cent titratable acidity of cow skim milk fermented with *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination is shown in Table 4.4 and Fig. 4.4. An increase in titratable acidity was observed for *L. acidophilus*-I alone and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS as sugar per cent increased from 0.0 to 7.0 and then followed decreasing trend as sugar per cent increased further from 7.0 to 9.0 per cent, irrespective of strains used. The titratable acidity produced by *L. acidophilus*-I and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS differed significantly ($P < 0.05$), except at 5.0 and 7.0 per cent sugar levels. No significant difference in titratable acidity produced by *L. casei*-RTS was observed at all the sugar levels.

Table 4.4: Effect of sugar levels on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during incubation at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Strain	0 %	3 %	5 %	7 %	8 %
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^a	1.12±0.08	1.45±0.07	1.53±0.08	1.60±0.05	1.44±0.02
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS ^b	0.40±0.05	0.36±0.02	0.37±0.09	0.40±0.08	0.39±0.07
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^c + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	1.30±0.11	1.47±0.06	1.55±0.02	1.60±0.03	1.46±0.02

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of six replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial pH and % TA of sterilized skim milk were 6.5 ± 0.10 and 0.19 ± 0.02 , respectively.
4. The values in different rows differ significantly.

^aCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.1195.

^bCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.9985.

^cCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0518.

Figure 4.4: Effect of sugar levels on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Above observations show that the lactic acid produced by *L. acidophilus*-I with *L. casei*-RTS at 5.0 and 7.0 per cent sugar level did not exhibit markedly difference (CD at 5.0 % level of significance was 0.1195). Optimum level of 5.0 per cent sugar was selected and used in further trials.

4.4 Effect of inoculum rate on acid production

Table 4.5 shows the effect of inoculum rate (1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 per cent) on the growth of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination after 16 hours incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Increase in rate of inoculum from 1.0 to 3.0 per cent exhibited appreciable increase in acid production for all the strains tested. The per cent titratable acidity for *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination at the end of 16 h were 1.39 ± 0.02 , 0.48 ± 0.03 and 1.46 ± 0.01 , respectively at 3 per cent rate of inoculum, as compared to 1.22 ± 0.03 , 0.40 ± 0.01 and 1.31 ± 0.06 at 1 per cent rate of inoculum. Growth of *L. acidophilus*-I and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS differs significantly ($P < 0.05$) at all levels of inoculum with CD 0.0129 and 0.0793, respectively, whereas *L. casei*-RTS did not show significant difference.

Table 4.5: Effect of inoculum rate of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination on titratable acidity of cow skim milk during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Strain	1 %	2 %	3 %
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^a	1.22±0.03	1.32±0.03	1.39±0.02
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS ^b	0.40±0.01	0.45±0.07	0.48±0.03
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^c + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	1.31±0.06	1.41±0.03	1.46±0.01

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of three replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial % TA and pH of sterilized skim milk were 0.19 ± 0.02 and 6.5 ± 0.10 , respectively.
4. The values in different rows differ significantly.

^aCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0129.

^bCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.1411.

^cCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0793.

Figure 4.5: Effect of inoculum rate of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination on titratable acidity of cow skim milk during 16 h incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

The increased acid production by *L. acidophilus*-I and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS as a result of increasing rate of inoculum is in tune with the result of Agrawal, V. (1980) and Emmons et al. (1960).

4.5 Effect of incubation temperature on acid production

The effect of incubation temperature (30, 37, 42 and 50°C) on acid production in skim milk inoculated with *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and with their combination is shown in Table 4.6 and Fig. 4.6. Increase in incubation temperature from 30 to 42°C exhibited appreciable increase in acid production irrespective of the strains tested, being lowest in *L. casei*-RTS. The maximum increase in per cent titratable acidity for *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination was observed at 42°C which were 1.69 ± 0.03 , 0.44 ± 0.03 and 1.61 ± 0.03 , respectively as compared to 0.77 ± 0.01 , 0.21 ± 0.01 and 0.60 ± 0.02 at 30°C incubation temperature. Further increase in incubation temperature from 42°C to 50°C resulted decrease in acid production significantly ($P < 0.05$). Growth of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination differs significantly ($P < 0.05$) at all the tested incubation temperatures with CD 0.0518, 0.0441 and 0.0894, respectively.

Table 4.6: Effect of incubation temperature on titratable acidity, produced by *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination in cow skim milk

Strain	30°C	37°C	42°C	50°C
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^a	0.77 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.04	1.69 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.02
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS ^b	0.21 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.01
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^c + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	0.60 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.06	1.61 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.02

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of three replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial % TA and pH of sterilized skim milk were 0.19 ± 0.02 and 6.5 ± 0.10 , respectively.
4. The values in different rows differ significantly.

^aCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0518.

^bCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0441.

^cCD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0894.

Figure 4.6: Effect of incubation temperature on titratable acidity, produced by *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination in cow skim milk

Incubation temperature is one of the most important environmental factors that influence the biochemical characteristics of lactic cultures. Although the role of incubation temperature on acid, flavour production and proteolytic activity by lactic acid bacteria has been studied by many workers (Accolas et al., 1977; Babel, 1946; Pack et al., 1968 and Singh et al., 1980), a wide range of optimum temperatures have been recommended for acid production by starters. It is clear from Table 4.6 that samples incubated at 42°C produced significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher titratable acidity in comparison to other temperatures. Therefore incubation temperature of 42°C was selected for the preparation of yoghurt like product. The incubation temperature of 42°C was also recommended by ToDoric and Bajic (1979) for the preparation of yoghurt.

4.6 Effect of total solids on acid production

Effect of supplementation of cow skim milk with 2.0, 3.0 and 5.0 per cent skim milk powder on acid production by *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ is shown in Table 4.7 and Fig. 4.7.

It is apparent from above table that acid produced by the tested strains was maximum at 5.0 per cent supplementation level. The titratable acidity values at the end of 16 h in skim milk supplemented with 5.0 per cent skim milk powder for *L. acidophilus*, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination were 1.26 ± 0.01 , 0.44 ± 0.03 and 1.37 ± 0.03 , respectively, as compared to 1.19 ± 0.02 , 0.41 ± 0.01 and 1.31 ± 0.04 , respectively at 2.0 per cent supplementation level.

Growth of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination differed significantly at 2.0 and 5.0 per cent supplementation levels of skim milk powder and showed non-significant difference at 3.0 and 5.0 per cent levels.

Table 4.7: Effect of skim milk powder addition on titratable acidity of cow skim milk using *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Strain	2 %	3 %	5 %
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^a	1.19 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.01	1.26 ± 0.01
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS ^b	0.41 ± 0.01	0.43 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.03
<i>L. acidophilus</i> -I ^c + <i>L. casei</i> -RTS	1.31 ± 0.04	1.35 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.03

1. All values are expressed as mean \pm Sd of three replications and represent 16 h incubation period using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial % TA, pH and total solid content of sterilized skim milk were 0.19 ± 0.02 , 6.5 ± 0.1 and 8.87 ± 0.06 , respectively.
4. The values in different rows differ significantly.

^a CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0631.

^b CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.0493.

^c CD at 5 % level of significance is 0.1013.

Figure 4.7: Effect of total solid content on titratable acidity of cow skim milk, using *L. acidophilus-I*, *L. casei-RTS* and their combination during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

ToDoric and Bajic (1979) reported that addition of skim milk powder during yoghurt manufacture ranging from 0.5 to 3.0 % improved satisfactorily the viscosity of product and markedly accelerated acid production. In present study the optimized level of total solids used to manufacture yoghurt like product is 14 per cent (5 % added skim milk powder) and it is further observed that higher levels of total solids decreased acid production rate. Our results confirm the findings of Tamime and Deetha (1980) that optimum quality of low fat yoghurt manufactured from milk containing 14-15 per cent total milk solids.

4.7 Effect of different pH and bile salt concentrations on the growth of *L. casei* strains during 16 hrs incubation at 37°C .

Table 4.8 and 4.9 show the effect of pH on the growth of *L. casei-RTS* and *L. casei-300* at different hours. Both the strains were unable to grow at pH 4. At pH 5 and 6, their growth

inhibited and was higher at pH 6.9. However, there was variation in their growth at different hours. *L. casei*-RTS showed highest growth at all the tested pH at the end of 18 hours (Fig. 4.8).

Table 4.8: Survivability of L. casei-RTS in lactic broth at different pH during 16 hrs incubation at 37±1°C

pH	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
pH4	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
pH5	0.01	0.15	0.41	0.58	0.72
pH6	0.01	0.14	0.40	0.73	0.85
pH6.9	0.01	0.26	0.51	0.77	0.95

1. Values are average of two determinations and represent O.D. at 620 nm wavelength, using 1 % inoculum rate.

Table 4.9: Survivability of L. casei-300 in lactic broth at different pH during 16 hrs incubation at 37±1°C

pH	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
pH4	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02
pH5	0.01	0.22	0.37	0.46	0.62
pH6	0.01	0.11	0.38	0.68	0.76
pH6.9	0.01	0.40	0.70	0.70	0.80

1. Values are average of two determinations and represent O.D. at 620 nm wavelength, using 1 % inoculum rate.

Figure 4.8: Effect of *L. casei* strains on optical density of lactic broth at different pH during incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Table 4.10: Survivability of *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 in lactic broth containing 0.3 % sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Strains	Optical density (at 620 nm)				
	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS	0.01	0.09	0.16	0.29	0.31
<i>L. casei</i> -300	0.01	0.06	0.18	0.24	0.25

1. Values are average of two determinations and represent O.D. at 620 nm wavelength, using 1 % inoculum rate.

Figure 4.9: Effect of *L. casei* strains on optical density of lactic broth containing 0.3 per cent sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Table 4.11: Growth inhibition of *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 in presence of sodium glycolate during 16 hrs incubation at $37\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$

Strains	Time	Optical density (at 620 nm)		
		Lactic broth	Lactic broth + 0.3 sodium glycolate	% inhibition
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS	8	0.51	0.16	69.8
	16	0.91	0.31	65.9
<i>L. casei</i> -300	8	0.70	0.18	74.2
	16	0.80	0.25	72.2

1. Values are average of two determinations and represent O.D. at 620 nm wavelength, using 1 % inoculum rate.
2. Strains showed complete inhibition in lactic broth with 0.5 % sodium glycolate.

Table 4.11 compares the optical density values attained by *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 in lactic broth and lactic broth containing sodium glycolate. Addition of 5 % sodium glycolate to the broth inhibited the growth of tested strains. However, 0.3 % sodium glycolate addition to the broth showed varied effect on growth on tested strains. At this concentration optical density measurement at 16 hours showed growth inhibition of *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300, which were 65.9 and 72.2 per cent, respectively.

For a beneficial role, an organism must be able to survive in hostile environment of gastrointestinal tract and proliferate (Sandine, 1979). Therefore, *L. acidophilus* and *L. casei* strains to be used as a dietary adjunct must possess the ability to grow at low pH and tolerate the presence of bile salts. In the present investigation, significant variations in the ability of *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 strains to grow at low pH and tolerate bile salt were observed. Both the strains were found unable to grow at pH 4 and in the presence of 0.5 % bile salts, but they were able to grow in presence of 0.3 % bile salts. This level of bile salt tolerance is significant as the same level is normally encountered in human intestine (Sjovall, 1869). In this study growth inhibition of less than 70-75 % in terms of OD measurements was considered as the indication of

bile salt tolerance. Accordingly both the strains *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 were found capable to tolerate presence of bile.

There is a great deal of variations in the pH of the stomach owing to presence or absence of food. It is likely that the ingested organism would come in contact with pH values in the range 2 to 8 (Franklin and Skoryana, 1971). Further, it has been suggested that destruction of the microorganisms in the stomach is pH (hydrochloric acid) dependent (Giannella et al., 1972). This bactericidal effect is very evident at pH values below 2.5 (Maffei and Nobrega, 1975).

In the present study, none of the *L. casei* strains tested was able to grow at pH 4. However, at pH 5 or above they were able to grow and showed highest growth at pH 6.9. Similar observations have also been reported by earlier workers (Toennies et al., 1950; Pilkhane, 1977).

4.8 Cholesterol uptake

The uptake of cholesterol by *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 strains was investigated in presence of 0.3 % sodium glycolate. Table 4.12 shows the detected amount of cholesterol in spent broth and cell pellets of the strains tested. Against initial concentration of 108 ± 8.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the amount of cholesterol recovered in spent broth of *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 was 73.1 ± 3.4 and 80.4 ± 4.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The corresponding cholesterol concentrations in the cell pellets of these organisms were 35.4 ± 3.6 and 28.1 ± 8.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. Thus, *L. casei*-RTS exhibited cholesterol uptake of 33.4 % as compared to 26.5 % by the strains of *L. casei*-300.

Table 4.12: Uptake of cholesterol by different *L. casei* strains

Strain	Cholesterol ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in		% Uptake
	Spent broth	Cell pellets	
<i>L. casei</i> -RTS	73.11 ± 3.41	35.42 ± 3.60	33.4
<i>L. casei</i> -300	80.42 ± 4.28	28.10 ± 6.12	26.5

1. Values are mean \pm Sd at 16-18 h.
2. MRS broth was supplemented with 0.3 % bile salt and 10 % pleuropneumonia-like organism serum.

3. The initial cholesterol in broth was 108 ± 8.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

It is reasonable to assume that an organism must be bile tolerant to manifest cholesterol uptake in intestinal tract. Therefore, the cholesterol uptake ability of *L. casei* strains was investigated in presence of bile salts. *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 exhibited cholesterol uptake of 33.4 and 26.5 per cent, against initial concentration of 106 ± 8.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Gilliland et al. (1984) observed that bile tolerance was important with regard to capability of an organism to survive in intestinal tract. Later on, Gilliland et al. (1985) found that uptake of cholesterol occurred only when the culture was growing in presence of bile. Gilliland and Walker (1990) tested different *Lactobacilli* strains and observed significant variations among them with respect to bile tolerance and ability to assimilate cholesterol. However, they did not observe any apparent relationship between cholesterol uptake and growth of test strains in presence of bile.

4.9 Antagonistic activity

L. acidophilus-I and *L. casei*-RTS were examined for their antagonistic activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Among these, only *L. acidophilus*-I showed inhibitory activity against pathogenic bacteria tested in this investigation.

4.9.1 Activity of milk culture filtrates

The antagonistic activity of culture filtrate obtained by fermenting milk with *L. acidophilus*-I strain is shown in Table 4.13. The culture filtrate of the strain *L. casei*-RTS did not exhibit inhibitory effect against the tested pathogenic bacteria.

The range of inhibitory zones for *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi* were, 17.64 ± 0.14 , 17.03 ± 0.21 and 16.42 ± 0.08 mm for milk culture filtrate obtained from *L. acidophilus*-I. The inhibitions of these pathogenic bacteria are depicted in Figs. 4.10.

(a) *Escherichia coli*

(b) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Figure 4.10: Inhibitory zones developed by milk culture filtrate of (A) *L. acidophilus*-I and (B) *L. casei*-RTS against pathogenic bacteria

Note: Inhibitory zone around the well indicates antagonistic activity.

Note: Inhibitory zone around the well indicates antagonistic activity.

Figure 4.11: Inhibitory zones developed by milk culture filtrate of (A) *L. acidophilus*-I and (B) *L. casei*-RTS against *Salmonella typhi*

Table 4.13: Inhibitory zones for different pathogenic bacteria, developed by milk culture filtrate obtained from *L. acidophilus*-I

Pathogenic organism	Inhibitory zones diameter (mm)
<i>E. coli</i>	17.64±0.14
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	17.03±0.21
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	16.42±0.08

1. Values are mean ± S.D and include well diameter (9.78±0.03 mm).
2. Values determined at the end of 24 hrs.

Since *L. acidophilus* inhibits the growth of intestinal and food borne pathogens, it has been recommended alone or in combination with antibiotics in the treatment of gastrointestinal disorders (Mikolajcik et al., 1975; Gilliland et al., 1977; Hosono et al., 1977; Mehta et al., 1983; Prasad and Gandhi, 1987; Kivanc, 1990; Mital et al., 1992). The exact mechanism of antagonistic activity of *L. acidophilus* is not clearly understood. However, the researches conducted in the recent past indicate that the antagonistic activity of this organism may be attributed to both acid development and elaboration of antimicrobial substances (Choi et al., 1984; Ferreira et al., 1988; McGroarty et al., 1988; Gilliland, 1989; Vervaeck et al., 1990; Lortic et al., 1992; Vignolo et al., 1993). Various *L. acidophilus* strains have been reported to elaborate antimicrobial substances such as lactocidin (Vincent et al., 1959) acidolin (Hamdan and Mikolajcik, 1974) and acidophilin (Shahani et al., 1977). Menta et al. (1983) found that *L. acidophilus*-AC1 produced a broad spectrum inhibitor that was effective against many gram-positive and gram-negative organisms. Barefoot and Klaenhammer (1984) have reported that some *L. acidophilus* strains produce lactacin B, a bacteriocin, that is effective against *L. leichmannii*, *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*, *L. helveticus* and *L. lactis*. It has also been suggested that *L. acidophilus* strains apparently are capable of producing more than one inhibitory systems and the antagonistic action, they exert towards intestinal pathogens results likely from the involvement of more than one particular inhibitor.

Milk is an ideal medium for facilitating ingestion of *Lactobacilli*. Therefore, antagonistic activities of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS strains were examined in milk.

Further, it is possible that antagonistic activity manifested by particular strain in broth may not be exhibited in milk. Significant variations in antagonistic activity of *L. acidophilus*-I against *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi* was observed. Whereas, *L. casei*-RTS did not exert antagonistic action against these pathogens. However several investigators (Choi et al., 1984; McGroarty et al., 1988; Kivanc, 1990; Suriani et al., 1993) have reported that some strains of *L. casei* displayed strong bactericidal properties against commonly known intestinal and food borne pathogens. This could attribute a variation among the strains of *L. casei* and it has been already reported that one strain may not produce all the types of inhibitory compounds that have been attributed this particular species of bacteria (Choi et al., 1984; Vignolo et al., 1993).

4.10 Studies on growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS and their combination in standardized cow milk

Growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ is given in Table 4.14. It is apparent from table that initial viable count was 3.7×10^5 cfu/ml, which increased at faster rate during first 12 hours and then increased at very slow rate, reaching to 1.10×10^8 cfu/ml after 16 hrs of incubation. Initial viable count in case of *L. casei*-RTS was more (1.75×10^6 cfu/ml) in comparison to *L. acidophilus*-I (Table 4.15). The viable counts increased at more or less same rate being maximum for *L. acidophilus*-I and lowest for *L. casei*-RTS after 16 hrs of incubation. The initial titratable acidity was 0.21 per cent being maximum (1.54 %) with *L. acidophilus*-I and minimum (0.43 %) with *L. casei*-RTS.

Table 4.14: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Growth characteristics	Incubation period (hours)				
	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
Viable count	3.7×10^5	2.68×10^6	2.57×10^7	8.07×10^7	1.10×10^8
TA %	0.21	0.24	0.44	0.95	1.54
pH	6.50	6.35	5.50	4.32	3.75

Growth characteristics	Incubation period (hours)				
	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
Generation time (min)	-	-	-	-	116.8
Rate of acid prodn ($\mu\text{M}/\text{sec}$)	0.00	0.23	1.54	3.93	4.55
Lactose utilization (%)	0.00	0.33	4.41	15.11	23.93
Soluble N (%)	0.08	0.12	0.17	0.20	0.21
Acetaldehyde (ppm)	0.00	15.00	30.00	40.00	50.00

1. Titratable acidity expressed as per cent lactic acid.
2. Milk was supplemented with 5 % sugar, 5 % skim milk powder and 2 % milk fat.
3. *L. acidophilus*-I was used @ 3 %.

Table 4.15: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of *L. casei*-RTS at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Growth characteristics	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
Viable count	1.75×10^6	4.71×10^6	1.33×10^7	3.45×10^7	8.39×10^7
TA %	0.21	0.26	0.33	0.38	0.43
pH	6.52	6.11	5.97	5.62	5.51
Generation time (min)	-	-	-	-	171.9
Rate of acid prod ⁿ ($\mu\text{M}/\text{sec}$)	0.00	0.46	0.54	0.39	0.39
Lactose utilization (%)	0.00	2.06	4.13	5.67	6.54
Soluble N (%)	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10
Acetaldehyde (ppm)	0.00	10.00	25.00	30.00	35.00

1. Titratable acidity expressed as per cent lactic acid.
2. Milk was supplemented with 5 % sugar, 5 % skim milk powder and 2 % milk fat.
3. *L. casei*-RTS was used @ 3 %.

It is clear from Table 4.14 & 4.15 that titratable acidity increased at much faster rate with *L. acidophilus*-I in comparison to *L. casei*-RTS. The gradual increase in rate of acid production was observed upto first eight hours of incubation with *L. casei*-RTS and it followed slightly decreasing trend upto 12 hrs and remained constant thereafter, whereas it followed a gradual increasing trend with *L. acidophilus*-I during whole the period of incubation (Table 4.14). Obtained doubling time or generation time was more (171.9 min) for *L. casei*-RTS than 116.8 min for *L. acidophilus*-I during 16 hrs of incubation.

Table 4.15 shows higher per cent lactose utilization (2.06 %) by *L. casei*-RTS during first four hours of incubation, whereas *L. acidophilus*-I showed only 0.33 per cent of lactose utilization during these hours. *L. acidophilus*-I exhibited a higher rate of lactose utilization in comparison to *L. casei*-RTS. This could be attributed to slower production of β -galactosidase by *L. casei*-RTS, resulting lesser utilization of lactose. The initial soluble nitrogen was 0.08 per cent, which increased to 0.21 and 0.10 per cent in *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS strains, respectively after 16 hrs of incubation. This showed much higher proteolysis with *L. acidophilus*-I in comparison to *L. casei*-RTS. Acetaldehyde production rate was faster with *L. acidophilus*-I in comparison to *L. casei*-RTS. The final values of acetaldehyde produced by *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS were 50.0 and 35.0 ppm, respectively, at the end of 16 hrs.

Table 4.16 shows the effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I in combination with *L. casei*-RTS at $42 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Initial viable count was 1.12×10^8 cfu/ml, which increased at more or less steady rate during incubation period reaching to 9.54×10^7 cfu/ml at the end of 16 hrs. The viable counts at the end of incubation period for *L. casei*-RTS was comparatively lower than the viable counts for *L. acidophilus*-I individually and its combination with *L. casei*-RTS. This could be attributed to inhibitory effect on the growth of microorganisms due to higher production of lactic acid. Titratable acidity of sample inoculated with *L. acidophilus*-I along with *L. casei*-RTS was 0.21 which increased to 1.58 per cent after 16 hrs of incubation. Lactic acid production was much faster during first 8 hrs and then followed declining trend during rest of the period of incubation. The initial pH was 6.50 which decreased to 3.72 after 16 hrs of incubation. pH of the samples decreased at much faster rate during first 4 hrs and then followed more or less steady rate during rest of the period.

Table 4.16: Effect of incubation period on growth characteristics of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS in combination at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Growth characteristics	Incubation period (hours)				
	0 h	4 h	8 h	12 h	16 h
Viable count	1.12×10^6	3.58×10^6	1.79×10^7	5.62×10^7	9.54×10^7
Acidity %	0.21	0.69	1.37	1.52	1.58
pH	6.50	4.70	3.82	3.77	3.72
Generation time (min)	-	-	-	-	149.6
Rate of acid production ($\mu\text{M}/\text{sec}$)	0.00	3.70	5.24	1.15	0.46
Lactose utilization (%)	0.00	6.87	18.15	23.19	26.63
Soluble N (%)	0.09	0.12	0.19	0.22	0.23
Acetaldehyde (ppm)	0.00	20.00	40.00	45.00	50.00

1. Titratable acidity expressed as per cent lactic acid.
2. Milk was supplemented with 5 % sugar, 5 % skim milk powder and 2 % milk fat.
3. *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS in combination was used @ 3 %.

Table 4.16 shows that rate of acid production was highest during 4 to 8 hrs and lowest during 12 to 16 hrs of incubation period. During incubation period, rate of acid production was found related with the growth of microorganisms in the sample. Per cent lactose utilization in sample during initial 4 hrs was 6.87, which increased to 16.15, 23.19 and 26.63 per cent after 8, 12, 16 hrs of incubation, respectively. Lactose utilization in the sample was related with the lactic acid production during incubation period. Proteolysis in terms of per cent soluble nitrogen initially was 0.09, which increased at more or less same rate upto 8 hrs and then showed further increase at very slow rate. It is apparent from viable count that maximum growth took place between 4 and 8 hrs which resulted maximum production of proteases responsible for higher soluble nitrogen in sample during above mentioned period. Increase in soluble nitrogen was found related with the growth of microorganisms.

Flavouring compound produced by *L. acidophilus*-I alongwith *L. casei*-RTS in terms of acetaldehyde was highest between 4 and 8 hrs of incubation period. The final acetaldehyde production was 50 ppm at the end of incubation period. Acetaldehyde produced at much faster rate upto 8 hrs and then afterwards increased at very slow rate.

Figure 4.12: The changes in population of *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.13: Titratable acidity developed by *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.14: Per cent lactose utilization by *L. acidophilus-I*, *L. casei-RTS* and their combination during incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.15: Effect of *L. acidophilus-I*, *L. casei-RTS* and their combination on per cent soluble nitrogen during 16 hrs of incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.16: Acetaldehyde produced by *L. acidophilus*-I, *L. casei*-RTS and their combination during 16 hrs of incubation at $42\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

4.11 Storage Studies

Yoghurt-like product prepared by using the combination of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS was comparatively evaluated for biochemical and sensory characteristics with regular yoghurt during storage.

4.11.1 Proximate Composition of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product

Table 4.17 shows the proximate composition of yoghurt and yoghurt-like product as per the parameters optimized during the investigation. It is apparent that yoghurt-like product had more or less the same composition in comparison to regular yoghurt.

Table 4.17: Proximate Composition of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product

Parameters	Yoghurt	Yoghurt-like Product
Fat (%)	1.96 ± 0.06	1.98 ± 0.04
Protein (%)	4.19 ± 0.04	4.25 ± 0.06
Total sugar (%)	9.41 ± 0.21	9.91 ± 0.11

Ash (%)	0.94 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.03
Acidity (%)	1.21 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.05
Total solids (%)	21.91 ± 0.11	20.52 ± 0.16

1. Values expressed as mean ± SD of three replications.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial % TA, pH and total solids content of milk were 0.22 ± 0.02, 6.3 ± 0.10 and 20.89, respectively.
4. Milk was supplemented with 5 % sugar and 5 % skim milk powder.
5. Regular yoghurt was prepared using *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *S. salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* @ 3 % (1:1).
6. Yoghurt-like product was prepared using *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS @ 3 % (1:1).

4.11.2 Sensory and Biochemical Studies of Yoghurt-like Product Made from *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS

4.11.2.1 Sensory Characteristics of Yoghurt-like Product

Changes in sensory characteristics of yoghurt and yoghurt-like product made from *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS were rated normal by the sensory panel in comparison to the control sample. Two-factor ANOVA showed that flavour of yoghurt-like product and control samples did not show significant difference during the first 3 days, and then significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed on the 6th and 9th days of storage (CD at 5 % level of significance was 0.819). The yoghurt-like product was rated subnormal in comparison to control after the 6th day of storage.

Taste of yoghurt-like product was rated normal up to 3 days and then became subnormal on the 6th day. Statistical analysis showed that the taste of yoghurt-like product did not show significant difference in comparison to control sample up to 3 days; however, significant difference was observed with respect to control on the 6th and 9th day of storage ($P < 0.05$).

The texture of yoghurt-like product was rated significantly inferior ($P < 0.05$) in comparison to control sample since the beginning. Yoghurt-like product was criticized for slightly loose body and whey expulsion (CD at 5 % level of significance was 0.554).

Table 4.18: Acceptability Scores of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Days of Storage	Control (Yoghurt)				Yoghurt like product			
	Flavour	Texture	Taste	Overall Acceptability	Flavour	Texture	Taste	Overall Acceptability
0	7.92	8.57	7.64	8.50	7.85	7.14	6.64	6.71
3	7.71	8.42	7.35	8.07	7.35	6.69	7.00	6.78
6	7.35	7.78	6.57	7.14	6.64	6.07	5.71	6.07
9	6.78	6.78	6.50	6.07	6.50	4.85	4.85	4.35

1. Values are average of seven determinations.
2. Control yoghurt sample was prepared using *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *S. salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* @ 3 % (1:1).
3. Yoghurt-like product was prepared using *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS @ 3 % (1:1).

Figure 4.17: Changes in Sensory Characteristics of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

4.11.2.2 Biochemical Changes in Yoghurt-like Product During Storage

Biochemical changes in terms of titratable acidity, soluble nitrogen, sugar utilization and acetaldehyde production in yoghurt-like product and control are shown in Table 4.19. It is clear from the table that titratable acidity of yoghurt-like product and control sample increased at more or less the same rate. The initial titratable acidity of control and yoghurt-like product were 1.21 and 1.06 per cent, which increased to 1.38 and 1.22 per cent, respectively, on the 9th day of storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Titratable acidity showed a positive correlation with flavour development in control and yoghurt-like product during storage. The sample scored lower flavour points as titratable acidity increased during storage irrespective of treatments; however, flavour points decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) after 3 days of storage.

Table 4.19: Biochemical changes in yoghurt and yoghurt like product during storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Characteristics	Control				Yoghurt like product			
	Storage period (days)							
	0	3	6	9	0	3	6	9
Titratable acidity (%)	1.21	1.25	1.33	1.38	1.06	1.08	1.13	1.22
Soluble nitrogen (%)	0.23	0.25	0.29	0.35	0.18	0.19	0.22	0.25
Sugar utilization (%)	25.94	28.12	30.91	31.62	26.13	31.20	34.07	36.91
Acetaldehyde (ppm)	20.00	20.00	25.00	20.00	30.00	30.00	35.00	40.00

1. Values expressed as mean \pm Sd of three replications.
2. Titratable acidity expressed as % lactic acid.
3. Initial % TA, pH and total solids content of milk were 0.22 ± 0.02 , 6.3 ± 0.10 and 20.89, respectively.
4. Milk was supplemented with 5% sugar and 5% skim milk powder.
5. Control yoghurt sample was prepared using *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *S. salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* @ 3% (1:1).
6. Yoghurt like product was prepared using *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS @ 3% (1:1).

Figure 4.18: Changes in Titratable Acidity and Soluble Nitrogen of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 4.19: Changes in Sugar Utilization and Acetaldehyde content of Yoghurt and Yoghurt-like Product during Storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

The initial values of soluble nitrogen were 0.18 and 0.23 in yoghurt-like product and control sample, respectively, which increased at more or less the same rate during storage irrespective of treatments. The proteolysis in samples did not exhibit any correlation with flavour development;

however, per cent soluble nitrogen showed positive effect on textural characteristics of the sample which were criticized for loose body and texture.

Per cent sugar utilization was comparatively higher in yoghurt-like product in comparison to control sample; however, titratable acidity and soluble nitrogen did not show any correlation with sugar utilization during storage.

Acetaldehyde production in yoghurt-like product was higher (30 ppm) in comparison to control sample (20 ppm), which increased at a more or less steady rate during storage irrespective of treatments, reaching 40 and 30 ppm after 9 days of storage at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Acetaldehyde content in samples did not exhibit any correlation with sensory characteristics.

5. SUMMARY

The main objective of the present investigation was to develop a yoghurt-like product by substituting *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* with strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus casei*. Among the strains studied, *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS, individually as well as in combination, were selected and studied for growth characteristics and biochemical changes to optimize the level of fat, total solids, sugar and incubation temperature. The strains were also examined for bile tolerance, hypocholesterolemic effect, survival at different pH and antagonistic activities.

The yoghurt-like product thus prepared using the selected strains and optimized growth requirements was compared for sensory and biochemical characteristics with standard yoghurt during storage.

The specific findings are as follows:

4. Among the strains studied, *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS were the higher acid producers, individually as well as in combination.
5. The optimized growth requirements for manufacture of yoghurt-like product were as follows:
 - a. Use of cow milk containing 2 % fat.
 - b. Addition of sugar @ 5 %.
 - c. Use of starter culture consisting of *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS @ 3 % (1:1).
 - d. Incubation at 42°C for 6 hrs.
 - e. Addition of skim milk powder @ 5 %.
6. Strains *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 did not grow in the presence of 0.5 % bile salt; however, they exhibited 65.9 and 72.2 % inhibition, respectively, in the presence of 0.3 % bile salt.
7. Strains *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 did not grow at pH 4; however, at pH 5 and 6 their growth was inhibited and was highest at pH 6.9.
8. *L. casei*-RTS and *L. casei*-300 exhibited cholesterol uptake in the presence of 0.3 % bile salt. The cholesterol uptake by these strains was 33.4 and 26.5 %, respectively.

9. Among the strains tested, *L. acidophilus*-I exhibited inhibitory effect against different pathogenic bacteria. The milk culture filtrate from *L. acidophilus*-I inhibited growth of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Salmonella typhi*. *L. casei*-RTS did not show inhibitory effect against these pathogens.
10. Yoghurt-like product prepared by using *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS did not show significant difference in composition, colour, taste and flavour, and was rated at par with regular yoghurt ($P < 0.05$). However, it was criticized for slightly loose body and texture ($P < 0.05$).
11. Yoghurt-like product had normal shelf life up to ___ days, whereas regular yoghurt sample showed shelf life up to 9 days at $5 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.
12. Per cent sugar utilization and acetaldehyde production remained higher in yoghurt-like product in comparison to control during storage. However, titratable acidity and soluble nitrogen were higher in control sample.

In view of the above study, it is concluded that yoghurt of acceptable quality can be prepared using *L. acidophilus*-I and *L. casei*-RTS in place of *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *S. salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus*. Yoghurt prepared as above could be considered to impart several health benefits, including control of serum cholesterol level and intestinal infections and disorders.

6. LITERATURE CITED

1. Abo-Elnaga, I.G. and Kandler, O. 1965. Zur Taxonomie der Gattung *Lactobacillus* Beijerinck I. Das Subgenus *Streptobacterium* Orla-Jensen. Zentral Bakterial Parasitenk Infektionsher Hyg. Abt. II. 119: 1–36.
2. Accolas, J.P.; Veux, M. and Auclair, J. 1977. Acid producing properties of thermophilus lactic bacteria in relation to yoghurt manufacture. Lait. 57: 1–23.
3. Agarwal, V. 1990. Studies on *Acidophilus* Milk. Thesis M.Sc., G.B. Pant Univ. of Agric. and Technol., Pantnagar.
4. Babel, F.J. 1946. Factors influencing acid production by cheese cultures. J. Dairy Sci. 29: 289–598.
5. Barefoot, S.F. and Klaenhammer, T.R. 1983. Detection and activity of lactacin B, a bacteriocin produced by *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. Appl. Environ. Microbiol. 45: 1808–1815.
6. Barefoot, S.F. and Klaenhammer, T.R. 1984. Purification and characterization of the *Lactobacillus acidophilus* bacteriocin, lactacin B. Antimicrob. Agents Chemother. 26: 328–334.
7. Benito-de-Cardenas, I.L.; Peral-de-Portillo, M.C.; Albizzati-de-Rivadeneira, M.C.; Medina, R.; Oliver, G.; Cardenas, I.L.B.; Portillo, M.C.P. and Rivadeneira, M.C.A. 1992. Effect of growth temperature on lactic acid and aroma compound production by *Lactobacillus casei*. Microbiologie Aliments Nutrition. 10: 349–358.
8. Benner, J. 1975. Production of D- and L-lactate in yoghurt cultured milk and kefir. Tierärztliche Hochschule, p. 68.
9. Briggs, M. and Briggs, C.A.E. 1954. The *Lactobacilli*: a review of the literature with special reference to taxonomy. Dairy Sci. Abstr. 16: 252–268.
10. Butler, C. and Beakley, J.H. 1960. Bacterial flora in vaginitis. Am. J. Obstet. Gynaecol. 79: 432.

11. Choi, C.S.; Chung, J.B.; Chung, S.G. and Yang, Y.T. 1984. Inhibition of pathogenic enterobacteria by *Lactobacillus casei* isolated from Yakult. Korean J. Vet. Public Health. 8: 49–58.
12. Cottennie, J. 1978. Yoghurt processing in Europe. Cult. Dairy Prod. J. 13: 16.
13. Curran, H.R.; Rogers, L.A. and Whittier, E.O. 1933. The distinguishing characteristics of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. J. Bacteriol. 25: 595–621.
14. Deeth, H.C. and Tamime, A.Y. 1981. Yoghurt: nutritive and therapeutic aspects. J. Food Prot. 44: 78–86.
15. de Klerk, H.C. and Coetzee, J.N. 1961. Antibiotic among *Lactobacilli*. Nature. 192: 340–341.
16. de Man, J.C.; Rogosa, M. and Sharpe, M.E. 1960. A medium for the cultivation of *Lactobacilli*. J. Appl. Bacteriol. 23: 130–135.
17. Dorothy, M. and Wheater, D.M. 1955. The characteristics of *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus helveticus* and *Lactobacillus casei*. J. Gen. Microbiol. 12: 133–139.
18. Dutta, S.M.; Kuila, R.K.; Arora, B.C. and Ranganathan, B. 1972. Effect of incubation temperature on acid and flavour production in milk by lactic acid bacteria. J. Milk Food Technol. 35: 242–244.
19. Elsadek, G.M.; Naguib, K. and Negm, A. 1972. Acetaldehyde and diacetyl production in Zabady culture. Milchwissenschaft. 27: 756–758.
20. Emmons, D.B.; Price, W.V. and Torrie, J.H. 1960. Effects of lactic cultures on acidity and firmness of cottage cheese coagulum. J. Dairy Sci. 43: 480–490.
21. Eskin, N.A.H.; Henderson, H.M. and Townsend, R.J. 1971. Biochemistry of Foods. Academic Press, New York.
22. Eyssen, H. 1973. Role of the gut microflora in metabolism of lipid and sterols. Proc. Nutr. Soc. 32: 59.
23. Ferreira, C.L. and Gilliland, S.E. 1988. Bacteriocin involved in premature death of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* NCFM during growth at pH 6.0. J. Dairy Sci. 71: 306–315.

24. Fetlinski, A. and Stepaniak, L. 1991. The trait of resistance of bile salts in *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Lactobacillus casei* strains as indispensable information in the data base for collection of industrial strains. Prace Instytutow i Laboratoriow Badawczych Przemyslu Spozywczego. 45: 185–190.
25. Franklin, M.A. and Skoryana, S.C. 1971. Studies on natural gastric flora: survival of bacteria in fasting human subjects. Can. Med. Assoc. J. 105: 380.
26. Giannella, R.A.; Broitman, S.A. and Zamcheck, N. 1972. Gastric acid barrier to ingested microorganisms in man: studies in vivo and in vitro. Gut. 13: 251.
27. Gilliland, S.E. 1989. Acidophilus milk products: a review of potential benefits to consumers. J. Dairy Sci. 72: 2483–2493.
28. Gilliland, S.E. and Kim, H.S. 1984. Effect of viable starter culture bacteria in yoghurt on lactose utilization in humans. J. Dairy Sci. 67: 1–6.
29. Gilliland, S.E.; Nelson, C.R. and Maxwell, C. 1985. Assimilation of cholesterol by *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. Appl. Environ. Microbiol. 49: 377–381.
30. Gilliland, S.E. and Speck, M.L. 1975. Inhibition of psychrotrophic bacteria by *Lactobacilli* and pediococci in non-fermented refrigerated foods. J. Food Sci. 40: 903–905.
31. Gilliland, S.E. and Speck, M.L. 1977. Antagonistic action of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* toward intestinal and food-borne pathogens in associative culture. J. Food Prot. 40: 820–823.
32. Gilliland, S.E.; Speck, M.L. and Morgan, C.G. 1975. Detection of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* in faeces of humans, pigs and chickens. Appl. Microbiol. 30: 541–545.
33. Gilliland, S.E.; Speck, M.L.; Nauyok, G.E. and Giesbrecht, F.G. 1978. Influence of consuming non-fermented milk containing *Lactobacillus acidophilus* on faecal flora of healthy males. J. Dairy Sci. 61: 1–10.
34. Gilliland, S.E.; Staley, T.E. and Bush, L.J. 1984. Importance of bile tolerance of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* used as dietary adjuncts. J. Dairy Sci. 67: 3045–3051.

35. Gilliland, S.E. and Walker, D.K. 1990. Factors to consider when selecting a culture of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* as a dietary adjunct to produce a hypocholesterolemic effect in human. *J. Dairy Sci.* 73: 905–911.
36. Gon, J.S.; Kwon, I.K.; Ahn, J.K. and Yoon, Y.H. 1988. Fermentation of milk by *Bifidobacterium bifidum* ATCC 11863. *Korean J. Ani. Sci.* 30: 618–630.
37. Gonzalez, S.; Morata-de-Ambrosini, V.; Manca-de-Nadra, M.; Pesce-de-Ruiz-Holgado, A.; Oliver, G. and Ambrosini, V.H. 1994. Acetaldehyde production by strains used as probiotics in fermented milk. *J. Food Prot.* 57: 436–440.
38. Gottschalk, G. 1986. *Bacterial Metabolism*. 2nd ed., Springer-Verlag, New York.
39. Grebus, C.H.; Mas, J.C. and Cremieux, A. 1987. Effect of various nutritive factors on the growth of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Bull. Assoc. Did. Microbiol. Nancy.* 23: 105.
40. Greene, A.K.; Geilman, W.G. and Cardwell, J.T. 1990. Comparison of growth media for culture of lactic acid bacteria. *J. Dairy Sci.* 73: 269.
41. Grienevich, A.G. and Makarova, A.P. 1974. Antagonism of lactic acid bacteria causing acute gastro-intestinal diseases. *Gastroenterol.* 78: 82–86.
42. Guirard, B. 1974. The amino acid requirements of microorganisms for growth. In: *Handbook of Microbiology*, 4th ed., Laskin, A.I. and Lechevalier, H.A. (Eds.), CRC Press, Cleveland.
43. Haenel, H. 1970. Human normal and abnormal gastrointestinal flora. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 23: 1433–1439.
44. Hamdan, I.Y. and Mikolajcik, E.M. 1974. Acidolin: An antibiotic produced by *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *J. Antibiotics.* 27: 631–636.
45. Hansen, P.A. and Mocquot, G. 1970. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (Moro) comb. nov. *Int. J. Syst. Bacteriology.* 20: 325–327.
46. Hansen, P.A. and Lessel, E.F. 1971. *Lactobacillus casei* (Orla-Jensen) comb. nov. *Int. J. Syst. Bacteriology.* 21: 69–71.
47. Hargrove, R.E. and Alford, J.A. 1978. Growth rate and feed efficiency of rats fed yoghurt and other fermented milks. *J. Dairy Sci.* 61: 11–19.

48. Harrison, V.C. and Peat, G. 1975. Serum cholesterol and bowel flora in the newborn. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 28: 1351–1355.
49. Hepner, G.; Fried, R.; St. Jeor, S.; Fusetti, L. and Morin, R. 1979. Hypocholesterolemic effect of yoghurt and milk. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 23: 19–24.
50. Hood, S.K. and Zottola, E.A. 1988. Effect of low pH on the ability of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* to survive and adhere to human intestinal cells. *J. Food Sci.* 53: 1514–1516.
51. Hosono, A.; Yasutuki, K. and Tokita, F. 1977. Isolation and characterization of an inhibitory substance against *Escherichia coli* produced by *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Milchwissenschaft.* 32: 727–730.
52. Huppert, M.; Cazin, J. and Smith, H. 1955. Pathogenesis of *Candida albicans* infections following antibiotic therapy. *J. Bacteriol.* 70: 440–447.
53. Hurley, R.; Stanley, V.C.; Leask, B.G.S. and deLouvois, J. 1974. Microflora of the vagina during pregnancy. *J. Obstet. Gynaecol.* 33: 155.
54. Hutchings, B.L. and Boggiano, B. 1947. Oleic acid as a growth factor for various *Lactobacilli*. *J. Biol. Chem.* 169: 229–230.
55. Johnson, J.L.; Phelps, C.F.; Cumins, C.S.; London, J. and Gasser, F. 1980. Taxonomy of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* group. *Int. J. Syst. Bacteriol.* 30: 53–68.
56. Kandler, O. and Weiss, N. 1986. Regular nonsporing Grampositive rods. In: *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology*. Vol. 2, Sneath, P.H.A.; Moin, N.S.; Sharpe, E. and Hold, J.G. (Eds.), Williams and Wilkins, Baltimore, M.D., U.S.A.
57. Khattab, A.A.; Abou-Donia, S.A. and Donia, S. 1987. The effect of bile salt on the growth of some lactic acid cultures. *Egyptian J. Dairy Sci.* 15: 51–56.
58. Kivanc, M. 1990. Antagonistic action of lactic cultures toward spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms in food. *Nahrung.* 34: 273–277.
59. Klupsch, H.J. 1985. Man and microflora. *North Eur. Dairy J.* 51: 221–226.
60. Koser, S.A. 1968. In: *Vitamin Requirements of Bacteria and Yeasts*. Springfield, Illinois.

61. Ledesma, O.V.; deRuiz Holgado, A.P.; Oliver, G.; deGiori, G.S.; Raihaud, P. and Gaplin, J.V. 1977. A synthetic medium for comparative nutritional studies of *Lactobacilli*. *J. Appl. Bacteriol.* 42: 123–133.
62. Lee, J.J.; Kim, H.Y.; Shin, J.G. and Baek, Y.J. 1991. Studies on the changes of the physical properties and the shelf-life of liquid yoghurt stored at different temperature. *Korean J. Dairy Sci.* 13: 124–131.
63. Lipid Research Clinics Program. 1984. The lipid research clinics coronary primary prevention trial results I. Reduction in incidence of coronary heart disease. *J. Am. Med. Assoc.* 251: 351–363.
64. Lock, F.R.; Yow, M.D.; Griffith, M.I. and Stout, M. 1948. Bacteriology of vagina in 75 normal young adults. *Surg. Gynaecol. Obstet.* 87: 410–416.
65. Lortie, L.; Simard, R.E. and Lavoie, M.C. 1992. Characterization of the antimicrobial substances produced by four *Lactobacillus casei* strains. *Microbiol. Ali. Nutr.* 10: 389–400.
66. Maffei, H.V.L. and Norbrega, F.J. 1975. Gastric pH and microflora and normal and diarrheic infants. *Gut.* 16: 719–726.
67. Mann, G.V. 1977. A factor in yoghurt which lowers cholesteremia in man. *Atherosclerosis.* 26: 335.
68. Mann, G.V. and Spoerry, A. 1974. Studies of a surfactant and cholesteremia in the Maassai. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 27: 464–469.
69. Marshall, V.M.; Cole, W.M. and Vega, J.R. 1982. Yoghurt-like product made by fermented ultrafiltered milk containing elevated whey proteins with *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *J. Dairy Res.* 40: 665–670.
70. McGroarty, J.A. and Reid, G. 1988. Detection of a *Lactobacillus* substance that inhibits *Escherichia coli*. *Can. J. Microbiol.* 34: 974–978.
71. Mehta, A.M.; Patel, K.A. and Dane, P.J. 1983. Isolation and purification of an inhibitory protein from *Lactobacillus acidophilus* AC1. *Microbios.* 37: 37–43.

72. Mikolajcik, E.M. and Hamdan, I.Y. 1975. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* II. Antimicrobial agents. *Cultured Dairy Products J.* 10: 18–20.
73. Mital, B.K. and Garg, S.K. 1992. Acidophilus milk products manufacture and therapeutics. *Food Rev. Int.* 8: 347–388.
74. Molchanova, L.G. 1988. Antagonistic properties of starters in milk used in the production of margarine. *Maslozhirovaya Promyshlennost.* 34: 14–15.
75. Nahalisi, M.H. 1988. *Lactobacillus acidophilus*: Therapeutic properties, products and enumeration. In: *Developments in Food Microbiology*, Robinson, R.K. (Ed.), Elsevier Applied Sci. Publ., London. *Dev. Food Microbiol.* 2: 153–178.
76. Nielsen, J.H. 1988. Isolation and characterization of the lactose-hydrolyzing enzyme of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Dessert Abstr. Int.* 49: 1458.
77. Nielsen, J.H. and Gilliland, S.E. 1992. Lactose hydrolyzing enzyme from *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Cultured Dairy Products J.* 27: 20–22.
78. Nishiyama, R. and Kaya, T. 1969. Studies on components of KUKO (*Licium chinense* Miller) Part V, substances in aqueous extract of KUKO leaves effective in stimulatory growth of lactic acid bacteria. *J. Agril. Chem. Soc. Japan.* 43: 203–210.
79. Orla-Jensen, S. 1919. *The Lactic Acid Bacteria*. Andr. Feed. Host and Sons, Copenhagen.
80. Orla-Jensen, S. 1943. *The Lactic Acid Bacteria*, *Erganzungsband* Ejnar Munksgaard, Copenhagen.
81. Pack, M.Y.; Vedamuthu, E.R.; Sandine, W.E.; Elliker, P.R. and Lessment, H. 1968. Effect of temperature on growth and diacetyl production by aroma bacteria in single and mixed strain starter culture. *J. Dairy Sci.* 51: 339–344.
82. Pilkhane, S.V. 1977. The energetics of *Lactobacillus casei*. *Dessert Abstr. Int.* 37: 3272.
83. Prasad, M.M. and Ghodeker, D.R. 1991. Antimicrobial activity of *Lactobacilli* isolated from fermented milk products. *Cultured Dairy Products J.* 26: 2.
84. Prasad, R.V. and Gandhi, D.N. 1987. Factors effecting the production of antibacterial substance(s) in *Lactobacillus acidophilus* strain R. *Indian J. Dairy Sci.* 40: 74–77.

85. Premi, L. and Bottazzi, V. 1972. Hydrogen peroxide formation and hydrogen peroxide splitting activity in lactic acid bacteria. *Milchwissenschaft*. 27: 792.
86. Reigh, J. and Soska, J. 1967. The thymine less death and deoxyriboside less death in *Lactobacillus acidophilus* R-26. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 29: 62–67.
87. Rogosa, M.; Franklin, J.G. and Perry, K.D. 1961. Correlation of the requirements with cultural and biochemical characters of *Lactobacillus* sp. *J. Gen. Microbiol.* 25: 473–482.
88. Rogosa, M. and Sharpe, M.E. 1960. Species differentiation of human vaginal *Lactobacilli*. *J. Gen. Microbiol.* 23: 197.
89. Rogosa, M.; Wiseman, R.F.; Mitchell, J.A. and Disraely, N. 1953. Species differentiation of oral *Lactobacilli* from man including descriptions of *Lactobacillus salivarius* nov. spec. and *Lactobacillus cellobiosus* nov. spec. *J. Bacteriol.* 65: 681–699.
90. Sabine, D.B. and Vaselekos, J. 1967. Trace element requirement of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Nature*. 214: 520.
91. Sandine, W.E. 1979. Roles of *Lactobacillus* in the intestinal tract. *J. Food Prot.* 42: 259–261.
92. Savoy-de-Giori, G.; Font-de-Valdez, G. and Ruiz-Holgado, R. 1985. Effect of growth temperature on acid production by lactic acid bacteria. *Microbiol. Ali. Nutr.* 3: 243–246.
93. Shahani, K.M.; Vakil, J.R. and Kilara, A. 1977. Natural antibiotic activity of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and bulgaricus II. Isolation of acidophilin from *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Cultured Dairy Products J.* 12: 8–11.
94. Shin, J.G.; Lee, J.J.; Kim, H.Y. and Baek, Y.J. 1991. Studies on the changes in quality and sensory evaluation of stirred yoghurt stored at different temperatures. *Korean J. Dairy Sci.* 13: 148–155.
95. Singh, J. 1983. Influence of heat treatment of milk and incubation temperatures on *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *Milchwissenschaft*. 38: 347–348.
96. Singh, J. and Ranganathan, B. 1979. Activity of *Lactobacillus casei* and its gamma-radiation induced mutant in different types of milk. *Milchwissenschaft*. 34: 91–92.

97. Singh, J.; Ranganathan, B. and Chander, H. 1980. Effect of incubation temperature on acid production and proteolytic activity in milk by selected *Lactobacilli* mutants. *Folia Microbiol.* 25: 496–497.
98. Sjøvall, J. 1969. On the concentration of bile acids in the human intestine during absorption. *Acta Physiol. Scand.* 46: 339–345.
99. Sontakke, A.T.; Dave, J.M. and Sannabhatti, S.S. 1990. Lactase activity and lactose degrading ability in some human strains of *Lactobacillus*. XXIII Int. Dairy Congr. 1: 196.
100. Speck, M.L. 1980. Preparation of *Lactobacilli* for dietary uses. *J. Food Prot.* 43: 55–67.
101. Srinivas, D.; Mital, B.K. and Garg, S.K. 1990. Utilization of sugars by *Lactobacillus acidophilus* strains. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 10: 51–58.
102. Tamime, A.Y. and Deeth, H.C. 1980. Yoghurt: Technology and biochemistry. *J. Food Prot.* 43: 939–977.
103. Thomas, K.C.; Nambudripad, V.K.N. and Dudani, A.T. 1986. In: 17th International Dairy Congress, Munich, D. 455.
104. Tittsler, R.P.; Geib, D.S. and Rogosa, M. 1947. Taxonomy of the genus *Lactobacillus* with special reference to correlation of differential characteristics. *J. Bacteriol.* 54: 12–13.
105. Todoric, R. and Bajic, D. 1979. Effect of different quantities of dried milk on yoghurt quality. *Mljekarstvo.* 29: 156–161.
106. Toennies, G. and Frank, H.G. 1950. The role of pH and buffering capacity of the medium in bacterial growth. *Growth.* 14: 341–351.
107. Tramer, J. 1973. Yoghurt cultures. *J. Soc. Dairy Technol.* 26: 16.
108. Tuli, A.; Sethi, R.P.; Khanna, P.K.; Marwaha, S.S. and Kennedy, J.F. 1985. Lactic acid production from whey permeate by immobilized *Lactobacillus casei*. *Enzyme Microbial Technol.* 7: 164–168.
109. Vedamuthu, E.R. 1974. Cultures for butter milk, sour cream and yoghurt with special comments on acidophilus yoghurt. *Cultured Dairy Products J.* 9: 16.

110. Vervaeck, J.; Huyghebaert, A.; Moor, H.; Mey, L. and De-Moor, H. 1990. Antimicrobial activity of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. XXIII Int. Dairy Congr. 1: 198.
111. Vignolo, G.M.; Pesce-de-Ruiz-Holgado, A.A. and Oliver, G. 1988. Acid production and proteolytic activity of *Lactobacillus* strains isolated from dry sausages. J. Food Prot. 51: 481–484.
112. Vignolo, G.M.; Suriani, P.; Pesce-de-Ruiz-Holgado, A.A. and Oliver, G. 1993. Antibacterial activity of *Lactobacillus* strains isolated from dry fermented sausages. Appl. Bacteriol. 75: 344–349.
113. Vincent, J.G.; Veomett, R.C. and Riley, R.F. 1959. Antibacterial activity associated with *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. J. Bacteriol. 78: 477–484.
114. Walter, H.; Stanhut-Kliph, H. and Benner, J. 1975. Occurrence of D(-) lactate in fermented milk, yoghurt and kefir. Arch. fur Lebensmittelhygiene. 25: 48–52.
115. Wooley, D.W. 1941. Manganese and the growth of lactic acid bacteria. J. Biol. Chem. 140: 311–392.
116. Wylie, J.G. and Henderson, A. 1969. Identity of glycogen fermenting ability of *Lactobacilli* isolated from the vagina of pregnant women. J. Med. Microbiol. 2: 363.
117. Yoon, Y.H.; Paik, Y.J.; Lee, S.W. and Yoon, K.B. 1982. Studies on changes in substrate composition in individual and mixed cultures of *Lactobacillus casei* YIT 9018 and *Lactobacillus helveticus* YM1. Korean J. Dairy Sci. 4: 134–144.

VITA

Name : MANOJ KUMAR

1971 : 26th July, Born in Pantnagar.

1987 : High School from Pantnagar Intermediate College, Pantnagar.

1989 : Intermediate from same Institute.

1993 : Graduation from G.B. Pant University of Ag. & Tech., Pantnagar.

1996 : Post Graduation in Food Technology from G.B. Pant Univ. of Ag. & Tech., Pantnagar.

Address : I/34, Phoolbagh, Pantnagar - 263145

Special appreciation

Throughout my stay in Pantnagar, I have been immensely fortunate to have had a wonderful group of friends, who have been the harbingers of joy, happiness and enjoyment. The special thanks are due to Sir-Bisht, Jha, Aru, Keth, Lohni; batchmates- R.S., Ashish, Ajeet, Naeem, Rakesh, Alok, Pawan, Puneet, Vineet, Pankaj, Ajay, Vijay, S.K., Nitin, L.C., Manoj, Jane, D.K., O.P., Vishal and Sandeep Saxena. The way they shared my joy and sorrow, the way they insulated me from the vagaries of life bears mute testimony to the sheer magnitude of love they so liberally showered on me.

Thank you friends

Manoj Kumar
17.09.96